

Report on the EOSC Winter School

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Report on the EOSC Winter School 2026

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Terminology

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
BE	Stakeholder Brokerage Event
CDIF	Cross-domain Interoperability Framework
DCAT-AP	Data Catalogue Vocabulary Application Profile (a specification based on the Data Catalogue vocabulary for describing public sector datasets in Europe)
DG RTD	European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
ELN	Electronic Lab Notebook
EC	European Commission
EEN	EOSC EU Node
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EOSC IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
HE	Horizon Europe
HE EOSC-related projects	Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC and related projects supporting EOSC
INFRAEOSC projects	Destination INFRAEOSC projects in Horizon Europe funding programme
KER	Key Exploitable Result
maDMP	Machine-actionable Data Management Plan
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
OAEG	Opportunity Area Expert Group
OAEG1	Opportunity Area Expert Group 1 - Persistent Identifiers
OAEG2	Opportunity Area Expert Group 2 - Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability
OAEG3	Opportunity Area Expert Group 3 - FAIR Assessment and Alignment
OAEG4	Opportunity Area Expert Group 4 - User and Resource Environments
OAEG5	Opportunity Area Expert Group 5 - Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition and Upscaling
OAEG6	Opportunity Area Expert Group 6 - Open Scholarly Communication
OAEG7	Opportunity Area Expert Group 7 - Research Software
PC	Programme Committee
PID	Persistent Identifier
PS	Programme Subcommittee
SEP	Sustainable Exploitation Planning
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TF	EOSC-A Task Force
TF1	Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force
TF2	FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force
TF3	Health Data Task Force
TF4	Long-Term Data Retention Task Force
VREs	Virtual Research Environments
WS	Winter School

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Executive Summary

This document reports on the third EOSC Winter School, organised in Nice (France) on 27–29 January 2026 by the EOSC Association (EOSC-A), with the support of the EOSC Gravity project.

Building on the momentum created by the EOSC Symposium 2025 and the substantial progress achieved by the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, the EOSC Winter School 2026 among all stakeholders. The event was designed to align efforts, deepen collaboration, and ensure that all relevant EOSC structures and expert groups actively contribute to the implementation of the EOSC Federation.

The Winter School was co-located with a closed meeting of the EOSC Federation Build-up Group (26–27 January 2026). The main objective of this co-located format was to ensure that Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEGs), EOSC-A Task Forces, and EOSC Federation Build-up Working Groups work in a coordinated and complementary manner towards supporting the EOSC Federation. This format strengthened the connection between expert recommendations and governance-level decision-making.

Under the motto “Supporting the EOSC Federation”, the Winter School featured two related parts:

- EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event (27 January): A matchmaking session that brought representatives from the EOSC Nodes in contact with potential service providers from EOSC-related projects
- Thematic Tracks (28-29 January): Engaging sessions dedicated respectively to the (i) Federating capabilities and interoperability, (ii) resources, and (iii) competences and training related to Open Science

The Thematic Track programme was shaped by representatives of the OAEGs and EOSC-A Task Forces, who defined the focus and proposed speakers. Discussions were guided by the strategic priorities set by the Build-up Group, ensuring coherence between the priorities of the Federation and implementation efforts by the community. The outcomes and recommendations were discussed on the last day with representatives from all participating groups (Thematic Tracks, EOSC Federation Build-up Group, European Commission, and EOSC Nodes).

This report presents the outcomes of the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event and the recommendations emerging from the three Thematic Tracks. The recommendations and gaps identified by the Thematic Tracks can be summarised as follows:

Thematic Track 1 (Federating Capabilities and Interoperability)

- Define implementation guidelines for EOSC Nodes to enable federated search and other core capabilities with well-defined protocols and APIs
- Define a true semantic federation to enable combination and query of research objects across EOSC Nodes, based on the recommendations of the Semantic Interoperability TF
- Define federated data access and cross-node querying to enable finding resources across EOSC Nodes
- Include new Federating Capabilities, including PIDs, support for machine-actionable resources, standardised, dynamic way to identify who offers a specific capability, stronger focus on scientific usage/use cases and workflows

Thematic Track 2 (Resources)

- Define minimal requirements for services
- Raise awareness of dependencies at the EOSC Nodes and at Federation level
- Implement domain-specific data quality validation services
- Address data quality at the service (data sources) and data registries level
- Data retention: Develop clear sustainability and business models for the EOSC Federation

Thematic Track 3 (Competences and Training)

- Establish and endorse a Competencies and Training Working Group in the EOSC Federation Build-up Group
- Make training resources findable in the EOSC Federation
- Make Competence Centres a core functionality of the EOSC Nodes
- OAEG5 to support the definition of a suitable model for including skills and training in the structure of EOSC Nodes

Overall, the EOSC Winter School 2026 deepened the collaboration across the wider EOSC community and strengthened alignment with the EOSC Federation Build-up Group. It also clarified critical next steps required in 2026 to ensure that the evolution of governance of the Federation, the Federating Capabilities, sustainability, and security frameworks mature in step with political ambition. A fourth edition of the EOSC Winter School is foreseen for early 2027, with the support of the EOSC Gravity project.

1 Introduction: Supporting the EOSC Federation

The EOSC Winter School (WS for short), already in its third edition, has established itself as a key event for the EOSC community. Experts from all over Europe value the Winter School format as an opportunity for in-depth discussions, strategic dialogue, networking, and first-hand insights into the latest developments of the EOSC Federation.

Under the motto *“Supporting the EOSC Federation”*, the Winter School fostered convergence through three complementary approaches:

- Enabling dialogue and mutual learning between EOSC Nodes and the wider EOSC community to support future applications and resource onboarding
- Providing structured opportunities for networking and alliance-building
- Enhancing collaboration through in-depth thematic discussions and hands-on working sessions

Building on the momentum of the EOSC Symposium 2025 and the progress achieved by the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, the Winter School 2026 further strengthened alignment among all stakeholders. The event was designed to coordinate efforts, deepen collaboration, and ensure that relevant EOSC structures and expert groups actively contribute to the practical implementation of the Federation. The combination of strategic guidance from the EOSC Association with bottom-up work from the EOSC expert pool to flesh out the programme is increasingly perceived as the place to be for everyone interested in the success of the emerging EOSC Federation.

1.1 High-level programme and structure

The EOSC Winter School 2026 was organised as a three-day-event, with a co-located meeting of the EOSC Federation Build-up Group the day before (only for EOSC Nodes). The event introduced the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event as novelty: a matchmaking session to bring representatives from the EOSC Nodes in contact with service providers (which could be from any of the EOSC expert groups, INFRAEOSC projects, and beyond). The “core” Winter School was spread out over 1.5 days, consisting of three Thematic Tracks (parallel sessions), followed by a morning reporting session on the closing day (see Figure 1 below for details).

Figure 1: The high-level Programme of the EOSC Winter School 2026

1.2 EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event: Where EOSC Nodes meet service providers

The EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event brought together representatives of the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, EOSC Nodes, and resource providers to facilitate the onboarding of mature services, datasets, and digital artefacts into the EOSC Federation. Designed as a structured “business speed-dating” exercise supported by a dedicated matchmaking platform, the event enabled 202 participants to engage in 281 pre-booked bilateral meetings, fostering targeted exchanges across European 24 countries. Participant feedback was very positive, highlighting the efficiency of the matchmaking format, the value of direct engagement with EOSC Nodes, and the opportunity to establish concrete follow-up actions. Key lessons emphasise the importance of thorough preparation, high-quality participant profiles, and clear on-site logistics to maximise the impact of short, focused meetings. Overall, the event demonstrated its effectiveness as a scalable and replicable instrument for operationalising the EOSC Federation and strengthening long-term collaboration within the EOSC community.

1.3 Giving directions: Thematic Tracks and strategic priorities of the EOSC Federation

The Winter School programme was shaped by the strategic priorities and gaps defined by the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, leveraging their hands-on experience as key stakeholders. Guidance for the programme development was provided by the EOSC Association, in close coordination with the Build-up Group, ensuring that the Winter School’s overall approach aligned with the Federation’s objectives. The main strategic priorities addressed were:

- 1) Clarify the role of the EOSC EU Node in the Federation, and ensure procurement requirements align with the Federation's needs.

- 2) Refine the Federation’s governance structure: Develop scalable mechanisms for information gathering, consulting, and decision making as the number of Nodes grows.
- 3) Clarify federating capabilities: Collectively agree on functionality and interfaces for all federating capabilities, and increase involvement of the Nodes in decisions regarding solutions for federating capabilities.

Building on these priorities, Winter School participants explored gaps and challenges in three dedicated Thematic Tracks: (i) Federating capabilities and interoperability, (ii) Resources, and (iii) Competences and training. The Tracks were structured to progressively: identify potential solutions, analyse them to deepen understanding, and formulate actionable recommendations to feed back to the EOSC Federation Build-up Group.

Approach: The programme combined multiple session formats: lightning talks, interactive round tables, and plenary discussions. Each of the three Thematic Tracks followed the same structure, built around the following blocks:

- Session A – Identifying Solutions: build a shared understanding, survey the landscape of potential solutions, and highlight promising directions
- Session B – Analysing Solutions: assess solutions based on suitability, maturity, expected impact, and implementation timeline
- Session C – Synthesising: consolidate insights into recommendations and define next steps

This design ensured that discussions were both structured and dynamic, enabling participants to contribute effectively to shaping the practical implementation of the EOSC Federation.

1.4 Taking up the work: Programme Committee and Subcommittees

This subsection provides an overview of the Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEGs) and EOSC-A Task Forces (TFs) whose expertise shaped the three Thematic Tracks of the Winter School, and also offers a brief summary of the planning process, the Programme and Subcommittees, and the collaborative structures that coordinated the development and delivery of the event.

- OAEG 1: PIDs
- OAEG 2: Metadata, ontologies & interoperability
- OAEG 3: FAIR Metric & Assessment
- OAEG 4: User & resource environments
- OAEG 5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, and Upscaling
- OAEG 6: Open Scholarly Communication
- OAEG 7: Research Software
- TF1: Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force
- TF2: FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force
- TF3: Health Data Task Force
- TF4: Long-Term Data Retention Task Force

Planning for the EOSC Winter School 2026 started in August of 2025, and kicked off officially with the formation of the Programme Committee (PC), and 3 Programme Subcommittees (PS), in early October 2025, following a dedicated meeting with multipliers from across the EOSC landscape (EOSC-A Task Forces, Opportunity Area Expert Groups, and INFRAEOSC projects)¹. Programme Subcommittees were recruited from OAEGs, with additional members coming from EOSC-A TFs and INFRAEOSC projects, and started convening twice per week from early November 2025 until the week before the event to flesh out the programme, with guidance from EOSC Gravity and EOSC-A. An Organising Committee was introduced (with some of the same members as the PC) to oversee, steer, and execute logistical matters such as communication with the event venue, information materials for, and communication with Winter School participants, as well as event registration.

Registration opened on 24 November 2025 and closed on 12 January 2026, attracting a total of 185 participants, including 84 attendees from the Opportunity Area Expert Groups, 56 EOSC-A Task Force representatives, 2 representatives from the European Commission, 14 members of the organising team, and 25 EOSC Node representatives. The event featured 117 project representatives (including 62 representatives from the 2024 INFRAEOSC projects), as well as 67 attendees without INFRAEOSC project affiliations, 9 of which without ostensible ties to any other EOSC-related activities (EOSC-A Task Forces, EOSC Nodes, OAEGs), bringing fresh perspectives that enriched the discussions, particularly within the Thematic Tracks.

¹ For complete members lists for each of these groups, please refer to Annex I.

2 EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event

2.1 Methodology: Bringing EOSC Nodes in contact with service providers

EOSC Gravity has continued the dialogue established with the projects in EOSC Focus. The project defined a set of activities for 2025-2026 that culminated in the Brokerage Event (BE for short) at the 2026 Winter School. The idea of this event was to bring the Build-Up Group (13 EOSC Nodes, plus the EOSC EU Node) to talk to EOSC-related project representatives and other resource providers, to explore the possibility of onboarding mature services, datasets, and other digital artefacts in the EOSC Federation, and to give information to shape the strategy of resource providers to build tools and services suitable for this specific environment.

2.2 Preparing the Brokerage Event

2.2.1 Vision for the event at the venue

The vision for the BE was for all stakeholders to take the opportunity of a business-speed-dating format, during the 2026 EOSC WS, and meet as many relevant counterparts as possible, with the support of a matchmaking software platform (b2match). In particular, the vision was to facilitate exchanges between EOSC Node representatives and parties interested in providing resources to the EOSC Federation, such as EOSC-related projects, OAEs, EOSC-A TFs, and other resource providers from the broader EOSC ecosystem.

It was envisaged early on that the process would be supported by a digital platform. b2match² was adopted from the options explored. This platform allowed participants to upload informative profiles and clearly communicate the business opportunities they would offer or seek (e.g. collaborative development, services, products, project applications, etc.); it would also enable participants to request/accept meetings and support in scheduling the meetings. While a public landing page provided basic information about the event, only registered WS2026 participants would be enabled to access the platform, populate it with their information, and book meetings.

The BE took place on the first day of the Winter School, between 14:00 and 18:00. The BE comprised 14 tables assigned to each of the EOSC Nodes, as well as 11 “hot desks” for any other meetings. In order to maximise the number of opportunities for attendees to meet as many representatives as possible (in line with the speed-dating concept), the meeting duration would be limited to 10 minutes, with 5 minutes between meetings to allow participants to move between tables. A feedback questionnaire was made available to be filled immediately after the event; a follow-up survey will gauge the event’s impact after six months.

2.2.2 Stakeholder engagement

The idea of holding a brokerage event with stakeholders of the EOSC Federation as part of the 2026 Winter School was communicated extensively to the community through EOSC-A

² <https://www.b2match.com/>.

channels (including website, newsletter, EOSC Forum), as well as in emails and several online meetings with different stakeholder groups, including INFRAEOSC Project Coordinators (8 Oct 2025), Task Force Co-Chairs and OAEF Coordinators (23 October), HE INFRAEOSC Impact WG (29 Oct), and EOSC Federation Build-Up Group (18 December). Three training sessions were offered to registered participants between December 2025 and January 2026, one of which targeted EOSC Node representatives exclusively.

2.3 At the scene: Impressions from the meetings

The EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event has been an integral part of the EOSC Winter School. It has evolved from a “conceptual” matchmaking session to an intense, highly dynamic community exercise. Participants responded to the invitation with enthusiasm, resulting in over 280 one-to-one meetings. What had initially been foreseen by the organisers as an “experiment” quickly evolved into a structured, energetic, and purposeful exchange between EOSC Resource Providers and representatives of the EOSC Nodes. The broad participation and lively atmosphere reflected a strong interest in identifying concrete collaborations around the Nodes and other implementation opportunities.

From the very beginning of the session, the atmosphere in the rooms radiated both intensity and enthusiasm. The 10-minute time slots, supported by a visible countdown in a clock on the wall and strict table rotation, created a rhythm that kept discussions focused, concise, and pragmatic. Participants arrived well prepared, having studied profiles and offers on the b2match platform in advance. As many participants later highlighted, the quality and completeness of attendee profiles were instrumental in making each short meeting meaningful and productive.

The physical layout of the event allowed for smooth logistics despite the large number of parallel meetings. The arrangement of assigned tables for the Nodes and additional hot desks allowed participants to engage across the venue, turning it into a highly interactive “collaboration space”, rather than a series of isolated bilateral talks. The Node tables and Hot Desks hosted 133 and 148 meetings, respectively. Moving between tables became an integral part of the overall experience.

What stood out during meetings was the high degree of engagement and the practical nature of the conversations held. Rather than just introductory exchanges, the discussions frequently went directly into topics that explored potential collaboration opportunities, as confirmed by feedback from the participants collected via a Mentimeter questionnaire that queried about the impact of the event:

Figure 2: Matchmaking meetings between EOSC Resource Providers and EOSC Node Representatives during the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event (Nice, 27 January 2026).

- technical requirements for onboarding services into Nodes,
- organisational models of collaboration within the EOSC Federation,
- questions related to the second wave of Nodes enrolment,
- opportunities for joint proposals under EOSC Gravity and Horizon Europe calls
- training and upskilling.

The EOSC Academy concept was also presented as a collaborative initiative for mutual learning, under development within the EOSC Gravity project, and explored how training activities could support both Node development and service onboarding processes.

Many participants reported that the event allowed them to speak with individuals they would not have otherwise identified as relevant contacts. The diversity of expertise present at the tables (spanning national and thematic Nodes, resource providers, and project representatives) created a unique environment where different perspectives on EOSC implementation could be confronted and aligned.

Figure 3: Matchmaking meetings between EOOSC Resource Providers and EOOSC Node Representatives during the EOOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event (Nice, 27 January 2026).

The event also facilitated community-building and encouraged openness, peer learning, and mutual discovery. Participants appreciated the opportunity to hear directly from Node representatives about expectations, requirements, and practical challenges, and be able to present their own services in a targeted manner. At the same time, Node representatives reported that the meetings provided them with valuable feedback on their own service portfolios and helped them better understand the expectations, needs, and maturity levels of potential resource providers across Europe. The meetings often continued informally during breaks and the networking post-event reception, indicating that the scheduled interactions successfully triggered longer-term engagement.

In total, the event platform registered

- 202 participants,
- 281 booked meetings,
- 874 exchanged messages (as of 18.02.2026),
- 112 posted opportunities (as of 18.02.2026),
- 2442 profile views (as of 18.02.2026).

These figures illustrate not only the intensity of the on-site interactions but also the significant level of preparation and follow-up activity carried out via the matchmaking platform. The intensity of interactions during the event was further reflected in the individual engagement levels observed on the b2match platform. Several participants conducted the maximum possible number of meetings (14) during the session. Some profiles received up to **18 meeting requests**, while others exchanged more than **40 direct messages** via the platform's chat function, demonstrating how the event was useful to maximise contacts, explore concrete collaboration paths, and actively seek relevant partners across the EOOSC community.

The European dimension of the event was clearly visible not only in the diversity of expertise present, but also in the geographical representation of participants. In total, **24 countries** were represented at the Brokerage Event. The largest groups came from France (18

participants), Germany, Italy and the Netherlands (14 each), followed by Greece and Switzerland (12 each), the United Kingdom (11), Austria and Spain (10 each), Belgium, Czech Republic and Poland (8 each). In addition, participants joined from Finland and Sweden (5 each), Hungary, Latvia, Norway, and Portugal (3 each), Slovakia and Slovenia (2 each), Bulgaria, Denmark, Ireland and North Macedonia (1 each).

This broad geographical distribution reinforced the pan-European character of the EOSC Federation build-up phase, creating a unique environment in which national and thematic perspectives on EOSC implementation could be directly exchanged (see Figure 5).

Figure 4: Group photo taken during the Introduction to the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event (Nice, 27 January 2026).

2.4 Results and lessons learned

2.4.1 Results

The Brokerage Event achieved its primary objective of facilitating direct contact between resource providers and EOSC Federation Nodes and proved to be a highly effective instrument for supporting the practical build-up of the EOSC Federation.

The impact of the Brokerage Event should also be viewed considering its strong European reach. With participants coming from 24 different countries, the event successfully brought together a broad spectrum of national and thematic EOSC perspectives. This diversity significantly enriched the discussions and contributed to a better mutual understanding of the expectations, priorities, and operational contexts of different Nodes and resource providers across Europe.

Feedback collected through the post-event Impact Assessment Questionnaire (**83 respondents**) and other statements gathered during the Closing Session confirm the tangible impact of the event (Figure 5):

How many **meaningful connections** did you make at this event?

Was the EOSC Winter School Brokerage Event useful to **learn anything new** about products or services that you were not familiar with?

Do you think this event helped you **support the kick-start of an onboarding process** for your Node or for your services?

Do you think this event helped you increase **visibility** of your products/services as a provider or as a Node?

Figure 5: Results of the Post-Event Impact Assessment Questionnaire (Mentimeter survey conducted on 27 January 2026, 83 respondents).

- 75.9% of respondents indicated that the event helped them learn about products or services they were not previously familiar with.
- 64.7% reported increased visibility of their products or services as providers or Nodes.
- 42.4% stated that the event supported the kick-start of an onboarding process for their Node or services.

Participant feedback survey results highlight additional insights regarding the perceived quality and effectiveness of the event:

- Relevance of the event, attendees, and connections made: 4.1/5
- Satisfaction with networking opportunities (quality and quantity): 4.1/5
- Likelihood of engaging with connections after the event: 4.3/5
- Meaningful connections made at the event:
 - Very few (<10%): 5 responses
 - Quite a few (20-50%): 35 responses
 - A lot (>50%): 33 responses
- Likelihood of advancing opportunities identified at the event: 3.8/5

These results show that a majority of participants found the event highly relevant, made significant connections, and anticipates continued collaboration beyond the event. They complement the quantitative engagement metrics recorded on the b2match platform, underlining both the intensity and the perceived value of the interactions. Feedback also highlighted the value of connecting as individuals, making the format particularly relevant and valuable for increased collaboration between the Nodes and the INFRAEOSC projects.

The feedback collected after the meetings provides additional evidence of the substantive value of the interactions. **109 meetings received positive ratings** (4 or 5/5), and **80% of respondents** reported that the Brokerage Event helped them clarify open questions they had prior to the event. This quantitative feedback is particularly meaningful when considered together with the types of questions participants reported addressing during the meetings. Importantly, many participants emphasised that the event helped clarify open questions regarding:

- expectations of Nodes towards service providers,
- collaboration models between national and thematic Nodes,
- practical aspects of Nodes enrolment procedures,
- capabilities that Nodes may need to develop in the near future.

The level of individual engagement recorded on the matchmaking platform (including participants filling all available meeting slots, receiving a high number of meeting requests, and using the chat function to follow up) confirms that the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event stimulated proactive networking well beyond passive attendance.

Planned follow-up activities reported by participants include:

- onboarding of services into Nodes and alignment with technical requirements,
- further discussions on service integration and new use cases,
- training activities and contributions to EOSC Academy specifications,
- assessment of feedback gathered from the Node representatives,
- preparation of joint project proposals (Horizon Europe, EOSC Gravity, and others),
- strengthened public relations and dissemination activities.

2.4.2 Lessons learned

The Brokerage Event provided valuable insights for the future:

- **The matchmaking format is effective:** The combination of pre-event preparation, structured scheduling via b2match, and brief meetings with a defined timeline proved highly efficient for initiating targeted collaboration.
- **Quality of profiles is critical:** Participants repeatedly stressed that well-completed profiles were key to successful meetings. For future events, encouraging (or requiring) complete profiles, including photos and clear descriptions of offers and needs, would further improve outcomes.
- **Preparatory meetings were essential:** The preparatory sessions held ahead of the event had a big impact on the participants' readiness and understanding of the format and objectives.
- **Clear logistics and on-site support matter:** Printed schedules, table markings, countdown timers, and visible organisers ensured smooth transitions and minimised confusion despite the complex setup.
- **10-minute meetings are sufficient if well prepared:** While short, time slots proved adequate for focused discussions when participants had reviewed each other's profiles in advance.

- **The event stimulates long-term engagement beyond on-site meetings:** The high number of messages, profile views, and planned follow-ups demonstrates that the Brokerage Event is not a stand-alone activity but a trigger for continued collaboration.
- **Community building is a major added value:** Beyond matchmaking, the event strengthened the sense of belonging to the EOSC community and contributed to a shared understanding of the Federation's practical implementation.

Overall, the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event can be considered a successful pilot format that effectively supports the operationalisation of the EOSC Federation. The experience gained in Nice provides a strong foundation for refining and replicating this format in future EOSC events.

3 Opening Plenary: Setting the scene

3.1 Welcome address

The “core” Winter School opened with a warm welcome from EOSC-A Secretary General Ute Gunsenheimer, on Wed, 28 Jan 2026, who emphasised that the event is an important milestone in EOSC Federation’s timeline that follows in the heels of the 2025 EOSC Symposium, where the community celebrated the launch of the Federation with the first signatures on the Memorandum of Understanding, followed recently by all EOSC Nodes of the first wave. Marc Lemaître, Director General of EC’s Directorate General for Research and Innovation (DG-RTD) was quoted saying: “What matters most is to keep the momentum, ambition, and [...] you can count on the full support of the EC”, at the 2025 EOSC Symposium. The welcome address was followed by a brief recap of the meeting of the EOSC Federation Build-up Group the previous day, and a reminder of the open calls to support the growth of the EOSC Federation. Finally, it was announced that the 2026 EOSC Symposium will take place in Florence, Italy, in October.

3.2 Contribution from the European Commission to EOSC

Ana Teresa Mota (DG RTD) presented EC’s involvement in the creation and development of EOSC and the EOSC Federation. EOSC is a key element in EC’s strategy, together with the ERA Policy Agenda, AI strategy for data, AI in science strategy, the R&T strategy, and the infrastructure strategy, and is well placed to help progress its priorities, promoting the uptake of AI in science, developing AI s/w, tools and services. In the last two years of Horizon Europe, the EC will continue supporting EOSC with four calls, for a total of 98 million €, complemented by the funding spent in operating the EOSC EU Node via procurement.

Call identifier	Content
INFRA-2026-01-EOSC-01 (40 million €)	To accelerate EOSC adoption. 29 million € to be spent cascading grants (100,000-250,000 € per grant) to support integration of thematic research and RI communities
INFRA-2026-01-EOSC-02 (10 million €, 2-3 projects)	Trusted framework for secure and efficient data sharing in EOSC (EOSC Partnership). Proposals are expected to: develop templates and guidelines.
INFRA-2027-01-EOSC-01 (40 million €, co-funded by EU Member States)	Expanding and deepening the EOSC Federation - addressing national funders. Provide seamless access to EOSC users. Support the broadening, integration and structuring of the participation of research communities in the EOSC Federation.
INFRA-2027-01-EOSC-02 (8 million €, 2-3 projects)	Design business models, analyse opportunities and barriers. Develop case studies to valorise results. Evaluate possibilities of relevant types of licences for knowledge resources. Organise workshop, webinar, awareness-raising campaigns. Develop recommendations and best practices, based on case studies, operationalised by EOSC operations for uptake
INFO DAY: MARCH 18, 10:00-14:00 - ONLY FOR 2026 CALLS	

Creating the EOSC Federation requires a high degree of coordination among call participants. Current calls can be seen as an exercise for EOSC post-2027 involving novel funding mechanisms. There is still the risk of breaking the unity of EOSC if this process is not managed carefully, and mitigated by the open calls from EOSC Gravity and the EOSC Tripartite. Funding agencies need to understand that they need to fund EOSC, which will take time to be reflected in funding programs. Pressure from the EC and other stakeholders might help accelerate this process.

3.3 Evolution of the EOSC Federation

The EOSC Federation launched at the EOSC Symposium in November 2025 is a prototype that demonstrates the added value of the EOSC Federation to its diverse stakeholders and Europe as a whole. To become widely adopted by researchers, the Federation needs to mature to a production state that involves further development on multiple fronts, including but not limited to:

- A governance and funding model that supports a sustainable future for the EOSC Federation beyond the current co-programmed European partnership.
- The development of a cybersecurity model and completion of the set of Tripartite approved federation-level policies that adequately address the obligations and liabilities of the participating organisations.
- Refinement of the architecture of the EOSC Federation and revision of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF) to take into account the experience gained during the deployment of the First Wave Nodes.

The EOSC Federation MoU establishes a shared operational and interim governing framework to help in the transition to production status. The MoU outlines a refined operational structure for the EOSC Federation that was initiated at the Winter School with the following interim governance structures:

- Interim EOSC Node Coordinator Committee: main forum for strategic discussion, alignment of priorities, and endorsement of non-binding policies and recommendations;
- Interim EOSC Node Operations Committee: formed to address technical matters, with a focus on coordination of service and resource onboarding, advancement of interoperability, monitoring of technical implementation, and developing practices that enable seamless integration of services and resources across Nodes;
- Interim Working Groups – Thematic or technical working groups established to address specific areas and propose recommendations for consideration by the Interim EOSC Node Coordinator Committee.

The deployment of the prioritised Federating Capabilities (service monitoring, helpdesk, and service management system), beyond the federated AAI and catalogues already deployed, has been agreed and is currently being planned with a staggered programme that ensures their successful adoption by the Nodes. These developments will contribute to the revision of the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

Operational procedures that marshal the day-to-day operations of the EOSC Federation will be implemented. The FitSM standard has been agreed as the basis for organising the coordination of such operational activities. A means of testing and verifying that nodes are conforming to the operational recommendations and guidelines of the EOSC Federation also needs to be developed with the expectation that it could simplify the node enrolment process.

The process to expand the EOSC Federation is underway via the Tripartite's new enrolment call for the second wave of EOSC Candidate Nodes and two EOSC Gravity calls³. These initiatives mark an important step forward in the continued expansion and maturation of the EOSC ecosystem with an application submission deadline of 18 February 2026. The results of these calls will be announced in April 2026 leading to a staggered deployment timetable that will allow the successful applicants to be progressively enrolled/onboarded.

Bob Jones (EOSC-A Special Envoy to the EOSC Federation and co-chair of the Build-up Group) presented the Group's current status, including fresh results from the meeting held on 26 Jan 2026. With the first wave of EOSC Nodes now formally enrolled in the EOSC Federation, as per their signature of the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)⁴, Mr Jones stressed that the main task now is to keep up the enthusiasm and activity to continue progressing towards "production status", as described above. To achieve this, the Build-up Group has set itself the following objectives for 2026:

- Operational structure
 - Migrate the Build-up Group to the operational structure outlined by the MoU
 - Evolve the Federating Capabilities and the Interoperability Framework
- Transition to production
 - Move the EOSC Federation from "prototype" to "production"
 - Address legal/governance/operational engagement requirements
- Expansion
 - Enrolment of Nodes and onboarding of services and use cases (via EOSC Gravity Open Calls and the EOSC Tripartite Node Enrolment Call)
 - Leveraging the next wave of EOSC Nodes, Cascading Grants, and the projects awarded under HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-01

As the current MoU is not legally binding, and stronger binding agreements will be necessary as the EOSC Federation is moving towards production.

The challenges to be addressed in 2026 include expanding the usage and functionality of the Federated AAI and the Service Catalogue as main Federating Capabilities, and introducing monitoring and a helpdesk that integrates helpdesks from all Nodes. Furthermore, the different stages in which the Nodes find themselves must be taken into account; most likely, prototype

³ <https://eosc.eu/news/open-calls-to-grow-the-eosc-federation> These open calls support the enrolment of additional Nodes and onboarding resources and use-cases, and to work with the Nodes as well as the EOSC EU Node to prepare a schedule so new nodes, resources and use cases can be added iteratively to the EOSC Federation.

⁴ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/20251103_MoU_Operational-Preparation_EOSC-Federation.pdf

and production-stage Nodes will coexist in the Federation, and, similarly, the Nodes will include production and prototype services.

EOSC-A will leverage the upcoming enrolment waves and projects funded under the EOSC Gravity cascading grants and the HORIZON-INFRA-2025-ESOC-01-01 calls.

Mr Jones provided an overview of the objectives of the EOSC Federation for 2026:

- Onboard the new EOSC Nodes from the Tripartite calls.
- Implement the operational governance and organisational structure detailed in the MoU.
- Adopt FitSM, the IT Service Management standard developed with funding from the EC.
- Establish all necessary policies and the EOSC Interoperability Framework. In particular, the EOSC IF will be expanded to include cybersecurity and demonstrate cross-Node use of Federating Capabilities, including service monitoring and help desks.
- EOSC Federation users from all Nodes will be able to access resources via SSO and a common catalogue with clear access policies.
- Virtual Research Environments (VREs) support will be expanded.
- The corpus of FAIR, machine-actionable and high-quality datasets will be expanded.
- Communities and stakeholders will be provided with key information via the EOSC Federation Handbook. A new version (v3.0) will be prepared by the end of the year. The Handbook will be expanded to contain guidance for communities on Node enrolment and resource onboarding, via documented procedures and policies. Further, use cases from diverse disciplines will be added, to demonstrate the utility of multi-Node use cases.
- Ultimately, the goal for 2026 is to be able, by the end of the year (or at the 2026 EOSC Symposium at the earliest), to announce that the EOSC Federation has transitioned to production mode.

While significant progress has been achieved in enrolling the first wave of Nodes and defining the Memorandum of Understanding, the Federation remains in a hybrid state where prototype and production-stage capabilities coexist. The transition to full production will require not only technical stabilisation of federating capabilities, but also the maturation of governance structures, operational coordination mechanisms, cybersecurity frameworks, and sustainability models. The year 2026 should therefore be considered a consolidation phase in which governance evolution, interoperability standards, and operational processes are aligned before declaring the Federation fully production-ready

The first question from the audience concerned the boundaries of Nodes. Within the EOSC Federation, services hosted by a Node of any type will be used outside its constituency. How will the Federation deal with trans-Node exchange between services? Mr. Jones responded that many EOSC Nodes have had a federated structure in place before EOSC existed. In the EOSC Federation, the rules for Nodes to organise themselves internally have been kept deliberately loose, so that Nodes can define their internal agreements as it is fit for them when planning to join the EOSC Federation. It is accepted that there is no one-size-fits-all solution for this. The Federation is a system of existing systems, and it needs to make the most of what was already there to build something that goes beyond what any of them individually achieved.

The next question concerned the calls aimed at growing the EOSC Federation. In the Tripartite there is an agreement on high-level onboarding guidelines for services and new Nodes that can

be tailored by individual Nodes, but the Build-up Group recognises that there might be individual restrictions within Nodes. From the point of view of the Federation, there will only be one operational guideline to how to onboard services in a Node. It will be a decision of the Node to develop their own rules, as long as they adhere to the guidelines.

Some services do not fit well into the solution adopted for AAI by the EOSC EU Node. The EOSC Federation is still geared towards controlled access, with some catalogues being public, but others restricting access. Will EOSC-A provide any support for this transition period? Regarding AAI, users have asked repeatedly for SSO, so they do not need to login more than once. For this to work, declared access needs to be visible, not open to everyone. Further, it needs to be transparent and allow users to know which resources they have access to.

EOSC-A intends to support everyone in the EOSC ecosystem who wants to contribute to the development of the Federation, including TFs and OAEGs. EOSC-A would like outputs from OAEGs or projects to be adopted eventually by the Federation.

In her concluding words, Ms Gunsenheimer stressed the in-kind character of all contributions from the EOSC Nodes in building the Federation: there is currently no support from the EC, so the Nodes have to use their own resources (e.g. national projects or other funding streams) to fund all necessary activities. As a consequence, the Nodes need to be very selective about what they deploy and offer to users.

3.4 EOSC Federation Handbook v2.0

Rudolf Dimper (EOSC-A) presented the new version of the EOSC Federation Handbook⁵ on behalf of the editors (Andy Goetz from ESRF, EOSC-A and Miguel Rey Mazón from TU Graz, EOSC Gravity). v2.0 reflects the evolution of the EOSC Federation during 2025 and the experience gained by the Build-up Group. Besides updating the chapters according to the latest developments (a challenging task in a fast-evolving landscape), the revision has clarified the language employed as much as possible, to ensure the Handbook remains useful to all stakeholders. Major changes include an executive summary (absent in v1.0), an exhaustive abbreviations list, and an updated introduction. The chapter on governance has been updated to describe the Memorandum of Understanding and the new structure it has put in place, and the chapter on the EOSC Federation Architecture has been expanded to include details about the Federating Capabilities. Finally, an update on how to join the Federation has been added.

For v2.0, writers were selected from the first wave of EOSC Nodes. The updating process was based on the responses to a questionnaire on v1.0 sent to relevant stakeholders (EOSC Nodes, INFRAEOSC projects, OAEGs, and Task Forces) in early autumn 2025. The revised text was finalised on 23 December 2025, and then sent to EC for revision.

Looking back on v1.0, the process followed and its outcome is undoubtedly very positive: the Handbook has been useful as a concise manual for EOSC Nodes, and has been a steady companion during the EOSC Federation Build-up Phase, with over 5,000 downloads so far. The new version is expected to be even more successful; the new Candidate EOSC Nodes from the

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/18454649>

second wave will be asked to provide further feedback as they bring a fresh look. Feedback on v2.0 can be submitted anytime by anyone via email⁶.

The team of writers and editors have identified the update of the EOSC Interoperability Framework and of the chapter on research resources as the most urgent next steps. Work on v3.0 will start probably around summer 2026, with a new version expected by early 2027.

3.5 EOSC-A Task Forces: achievements and plans for 2026

Roxanne Wyns (EOSC-A Director, KU Leuven) summarised the recent activities of the EOSC-A Task Forces (TFs), who together with the OAEs represent the “brain pool” of EOSC.

The **TF on FAIR metrics and Digital Objects** focuses on assessing metadata practices across research completed projects, addressing the challenges of federating FAIR data by extending FAIR metrics focused on repositories. In 2025, the TF has designed, tested and deployed a survey for repository managers to evaluate interoperability, reusability, and FAIR compliance, while addressing challenges in handling sensitive data, access restrictions and data governance. This has been published (*Report on Repository Support for Data-level Interoperability/Reusability*), with a follow-up in 2026 to align with the evolving priorities of the EOSC Federation. In 2026, the TF will work towards enhancing interoperability and strengthen cross-Node collaboration in the Federation, ensuring that lessons learned translate into concrete improvements across repositories and services.

The **TF on Long term data retention** aims to provide recommendations on the retention, curation, and preservation, starting with a landscape report on the status, needs and challenges of scientific communities in data retention, appraisal, and re-appraisal. Two deliverables will be published by the end of Q1 2026 (*The Retention and (Re)Appraisal Iteration Logic (RRAIL)*; and *Current needs and challenges on data retention, appraisal and reappraisal across stakeholders and communities*, this one to be updated later in the year) to raise awareness in the EOSC community about these topics.

The **Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF** focuses on the technical foundations to enable the seamless access of users to data and services across the Federation by liaising with EOSC projects, research infrastructures and the wider community. Two deliverables have been published in 2025 (*EOSC AAI Architecture v2025 v1*; *Status of the Technical Interoperability in the EOSC Federation and initial gap analysis*), with one more under review (*Status of the Semantic Interoperability in the EOSC*).

The **Health Data TF** focuses on the interoperability, sharing and reuse of FAIR health data and services between the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and EOSC. The main objective is to identify all requirements, regulations, and ethical and legal foundations to enable access and processing of health data in EOSC in a fair and safe manner. The TF will foster interoperability with the EHDS for secondary use infrastructure (HealthData@EU) through the identification of common services and formats in EOSC Nodes. There is one deliverable forthcoming out of this

⁶ Feedback can be submitted via the following email address: handbook@eosc.eu.

Task Force (*Identification of gaps, redundancies, and possible synergies regarding different user journeys of researchers in EHDS and EOSC*) currently under review.

The TF configuration will be built on lessons learned and adapted to the rapidly evolving EOSC landscape. The roadmap for the next round of TFs passes through five key milestones:

- Q1 2026: The Brokerage Event at the WS 2026 to connect TFs, OAEGs, and INFRAEOSC projects with the Build-up Group;
- Q2 2026: EOSC Gravity will deliver a robust set of recommendations for consideration by the EOSC-A Board to define focus areas for next round of TFs, and optimise their size, remit, and deliverables;
- Q3 2026: Call for expressions of interest for TF members
- Q4 2026: Transitional handover period in which the Board and current TF co-chairs will work with the Build-up Group in dialogue with OAEGs and INFRAEOSC projects.

Q&A

Across the various EOSC Expert pools one can find roughly the same individuals in different constellations) working towards the same goals. Is this sustainable for the EOSC Federation Build-up Phase? A bigger momentum is needed. This could be achieved by simplifying and making more transparent the groups formed by EOSC-A. Ms Wyns emphasised the fundamental importance and instrumental nature of TFs for EOSC-A.

3.6 Opportunity Area Expert Groups

Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi (TU Graz, EOSC Gravity) presented the status of the Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEGs), the bottom-up initiative of the INFRAEOSC projects, to identify common challenges and synergies and facilitate collaboration across projects. At present, there are seven active OAEGs⁷. The organisation of the Winter School has relied, as in other editions, on active INFRAEOSC projects (21 as of end of 2025), from which OAEG members stem. The structure of the 2026 WS was however set by EOSC-A Board of Directors, who defined the three overarching goals (enable dialogue with the current nodes; bring the community closer to the Nodes; and enhance collaboration through discussions and hands-on work). In this setting, the core Winter School was developed by OAEGs in three “Thematic Tracks” with corresponding reporting sessions. The topics of the Thematic Tracks were guided by the challenges named by the EOSC Federation Build Up group, organised in three consecutive sessions, as explained below in chapter 4. The approach taken offers good chances of providing the guidance and support to the EOSC Nodes in their process of forming and joining the Federation.

⁷ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups>

4 Thematic Tracks

4.1 Methodology: Structure and breakout sessions

As described in the Introduction, the content and format of the three Thematic Tracks (**Federating capabilities and interoperability, resources, and competencies and training**) were developed by the Programme Committee, who formulated the overarching goals and ideas that were then translated by the Subcommittees into workable topics after an initial proposal developed by TU Graz (member of EOSC Gravity). This first draft was based on the outcomes of the 2025 Winter School, OAEF work plans, and the gaps in the development of the Federation identified by the Build-up Group. All three Thematic Tracks followed the same structure, with the following building blocks:

- **Session A – Identifying Solutions:** This session aimed to identify potential solutions to address known gaps in the EOSC Federation. It also helped ensure all participants shared a common understanding of the issues at hand.
- **Session B – Analysing Solutions:** This interactive session built on the outcomes of Session A, allowing participants to examine the proposed solutions in depth. Solutions were assessed in terms of suitability, maturity, expected impact, and implementation timeline.
- **Session C – Synthesising:** This session consolidated the insights from Sessions A and B into recommendations and defined next steps.

“Solutions” is to be understood here as “any tool, service, process, policy...” technically mature enough to be onboarded into the EOSC Federation, and that solves at least one of the gaps identified in the development of the Federation. All three Tracks employed a mix of lightning talks for Session A, followed by more interactive formats, e.g. round tables/world café for Session B, and plenary discussions for Session C.

It was also arranged that the outcome of the Tracks would be presented in a Closing Plenary on the last day. To complete the setup, the Subcommittees used this structure together with the challenges faced by the EOSC Federation (see chapter 1) to define the content of the sessions, including topics, format, and speakers. The draft programme, published in mid-November, was updated iteratively to reflect additional details and refinements.

The Subcommittees were guided by at least one facilitator from EOSC Gravity or EOSC-A (Stefan Reichmann (TU Graz, EOSC Gravity) (all Thematic Tracks); Brina Klemenčič (EOSC-A) for Thematic Track 2, and Isabel Caetano (EOSC-A, EOSC Gravity) for Thematic Track 3). Details on the Subcommittees and their membership can be found in Annex 1.

A comprehensive account of the work undertaken within each Thematic Track, including the main topics and presentations, is provided in Annex 1, while the following subsection highlights the key outcomes reported by the Thematic Tracks.

4.2 Key results and reporting from the Thematic Tracks

This subsection provides an overview of the key results and reports from the Thematic Tracks as presented on the last day of the EOSC Winter School 2026. Chaired by Stefan Reichmann (TU Graz, EOSC Gravity), the session featured 1–2 presenters per Track, followed by Q&A discussions. Given the complexity of the sessions, it was challenging to distil concise lists of recommendations, but the main presentations and discussions are summarized below (further details are provided in Annex 1).

4.2.1 Thematic Track 1 - Interoperability and Federating Capabilities

Thematic Track 1 was chaired by Diego Scardaci (EGI), Esteban Gonzalez (UPM), Tomasz Miksa (TU Wien), and Tibor Kálmán (GWDG). Thematic Track 1 participants represented a wide range of projects⁸, including four OAEs (1, 2, 3, and 4), as well as three EOSC-A Task Forces and other EOSC-related initiatives. Thematic Track 1 focused on the following key topics:

- Development of a metadata catalogue for classifying subject areas, maturity, scope of existing data sets, and resources
- Development of access models and cost structures (governance)
- Onboarding of the broader scientific community beyond the existing institutions

Tibor Kálmán reported on behalf of Track 1 and reiterated that in the present transition period, the EOSC Federating Capabilities are not yet enabled collaboratively by the Nodes. The governance structure of the Capabilities and their relation to the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF) are still to be solved. A new version of the EOSC IF is expected to come out during 2026. The main conclusions from round tables in Session B were presented next:

- **Round table 1:** FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) are registered in databases like FAIRsharing, but more (ideally all) key interoperability solutions should be registered in databases, so they can be leveraged. FIPs can play a role in EOSC to declare, share, and support implementation choices, and to help identify relevant implementation use cases, with the goal to progress automated usability and implementation.
- **Round table 2** considered three different implementations of FDOs in EOSC: PID-based, RO-Crate-based, and nanopublications-based. The round table analysed the different implementations and their possible interactions to prepare the Federation for adopting FDOs. The main challenges identified were how to implement FDO operations across different implementations, how to ensure interoperability between RO-Crate profiles, and how to transform all resources of EOSC into FDOs.
- **Round table 3** talked about adopting Interoperability solutions in the EOSC Federation, based on known gaps in the EOSC Federating Capabilities:

⁸ Participants include representatives of FAIR2ADAPT, OSTRAILS, EVERSE, EOSC Beyond, EOSC Data Commons, EOSC United, EOSC Gravity, CLIMATEAdapt4EOSC, CDIF4XAS, EOSC-ENTRUST, FIDELIS, Blue-Cloud, and EOSC RAISE Suite.

- There is a need for implementation guidelines for Nodes to enable federated search and other core capabilities, with well-defined protocols and APIs that can be used for data interchange.
- A real semantic federation (aligning vocabularies, resolving concepts, and navigating across knowledge graphs) is needed to enable easy combination/query of Research Objects across Nodes.
- A definition for federated data access/cross-Node querying is needed that enables finding resources across Nodes.
- The current set of EOSC Federating Capabilities needs PID capabilities.
- Support for machine-actionable resources (like FDOs) in all (core or federating) services is needed.
- Federating capabilities need to offer a standardised, dynamic way to identify who offers a specific capability (Node registry).
- Have a stronger focus on scientific usage/use cases and workflows

Cybersecurity was identified as a structural gap in the current Federation architecture. While federated AAI and service catalogues are being strengthened, there is currently no clearly defined cross-Node cybersecurity capability, including coordinated incident response, vulnerability alerting, penetration testing services, or harmonised maturity classification. Participants emphasised that cybersecurity must evolve into a recognised Federating Capability if the EOSC Federation is to operate reliably at production scale. Clarification of roles, including the potential establishment or operationalisation of an EOSC-level CSIRT function, was identified as a priority for 2026.

- **Round table 4** discussed resource categorization and resource profiles. Many concepts developed by the EOSC community have been implemented in EOSC EU Node, but have not been established as an official standard. The round table analysed 1) whether the EOSC community would like to acknowledge existing concepts for the EOSC Resource model and Resource Profiles as official standards in EOSC Federation; 2) whether adjustments are needed in current standards to serve the current and future goals of the EOSC Federation and Nodes. The table concluded with a collection of resource models and service categories used or proposed by EOSC stakeholders. There is consensus that current models and categories are a good starting point for the Federation and are for now the de facto standard, but more information should be collected from EOSC Nodes about what standards should be improved.
- **Round table 5**, on service discovery and interoperability, including EOSC-specific incident handling and mitigation, highlighted the following needs:
 - standardised metadata and automated discovery mechanisms to enable efficient service location and consumption;
 - build trust and sustainability between Providers, Nodes and Researchers;
 - establish an EOSC CSIRT to manage cybersecurity incidents across distributed EOSC Nodes;
 - service classification based on maturity levels, security best practices, and operational trust and security frameworks like SIRTFI, as well as a need for guidelines for best practices on operations, security and interoperability.

It was noted that cybersecurity across Nodes is missing as Federating Capability. This would require having

- “penetration testing” (simulated cyberattacks) as a service,
 - an alerting mechanism for EOSC relevant vulnerabilities,
 - clarification of the operational role of EOSC CSIRT,
 - support for developing incident handling capabilities of EOSC Nodes,
 - clarification of how to classify services based on scope, availability, and confidentiality,
 - support for joint security training and security exercises,
 - coaching on how to develop operational security, and
 - clarification of how to classify services based on maturity (POC, As is, SLA).
- **Round table 6** discussed different approaches to reporting metadata quality across scientific domains, including quality flags, processing levels, trust in the providing organisation, peer review, confidence scores from AI-based validation, defined Data Quality Labels, and automated compliance checks. Regarding metadata harmonisation, and integration, most domains rely on mappings and crosswalks, shared metadata schemas, and guidelines or standards officially endorsed by trusted bodies. (Meta)data integration implementations include the Virtual Collection Registry, the UDAL Data Demand Registry, and broker- or discovery-based solutions such as GEODAB and IDDAS. Evaluation and success measures for tools, standards, and guidelines include official endorsement by trusted bodies, wide adoption, availability of documentation, scalability, expandability, and support for complex use cases.

In summary, Thematic Track 1 produced a list of gaps in the EOSC Federating Capabilities:

- Implementation guidelines for EOSC Nodes to enable federated search and other core capabilities with well-defined protocols and APIs that can be used for data interchange
 - establish a clear process to discuss with the Node Coordination Committee the work plan for guidelines in 2026 for federating capabilities
 - agree on the standards to enable the federated search and other core capabilities (resource model, profiles, etc.)
- Define a real semantic federation (aligning vocabularies, resolving concepts, navigating across knowledge graphs) to enable the easy combination/query of research objects across Nodes
 - Based on the Semantic interoperability recommendations of the Task Force, discuss these recommendations with Operational and Node Coordinator committee
- Define federated data access/cross-node querying to enable finding resources across Nodes
 - Common way to query/use data cross-node: This could go to the Scientific Repositories working group, subject to its mandate being approved by the EOSC Node Coordination Committee (Q3/2026)
- Recommendation of new Federating capabilities:
 - PID Capabilities
 - Support for machine-actionable resources in all (core or federating) services
 - A standardised, dynamic way to identify who offers a specific capability (Node registry)
 - Stronger focus on scientific usage/use cases and workflows

- Security/cybersecurity across nodes is missing as a core federating capability

Thematic Track 1 highlighted the importance of multilateral discussions on interoperability and Federating Capabilities to avoid fragmentation or discontinuation. While exchange is happening across projects with the support of OAEs), there is currently little exchange with the Build-up Group. The Winter School provides an excellent format for this exchange, but happens too infrequently for this to be effective, but scattered discussions due to the different remits and decision-making processes across the various expert groups put them at risk of not being useful. EOSC Nodes, OAEs, Task Forces, and projects should establish sustainable collaboration formats⁹. Actions requiring decisions from the EOSC Federation require a more continuous process, but the focus should be on the Federating Capabilities.

4.2.2 Thematic Track 2 - Resources

The main results were presented by Chris Schubert (TU Wien) and Marek Cebecauer (Heyrovsky Institute). The priorities identified by the Subcommittee were as follows:

- Consolidate Data Quality knowledge across the EOSC
- Address data quality issues early in the data lifecycle
- Discuss the needs of service and resource providers
- Data retention and preservation in the EOSC Federation

These were discussed in three round tables on Data Quality and Trust, Services and Resources, and Data Retention.

The **data quality round table** identified the following priorities:

There is a need to consolidate Data Quality knowledge across EOSC initiatives, and to collect and align existing Data Quality expertise from INFRAEOSC projects (e.g. EDEN, FIDELIS) and EOSC-A TFs. In detail this could mean developing a shared knowledge platform covering Data Quality definitions, levels, and maturity models for EOSC, while building on existing outputs, particularly the work of first-generation EOSC Task Forces, to avoid redundancy. Furthermore, there is a need to address Data Quality issues early in the data lifecycle, i.e. to shift the focus from “last-mile” quality checks to early identification of issues, with a strong emphasis on capacity building for Data Stewards.

In terms of the impact of data quality, trust is affected by visible Data Quality: trust can be positively affected by improving quality processes, including validation against low-quality data and addressing quality challenges in federated environments through standardised protocols. Initiatives like GBIF and DiSSCo, who operationalise pragmatic “fitness for use” by defining both minimum and optimal requirements, could be used as examples. “Re-Use Fitness” needs explicit explanations to the levels of data management e.g. on prescriptive metadata and provenance information, metadata profiles, raw data, dataset, etc.

⁹ The collaboration formats established by EOSC Focus (OAEs, HE Groups) serve the purposes described above really well.

The **round table on services and resources** explored what is needed by those willing to onboard resources to the EOSC Federation and/or developing systems and tools populating it with data (beyond the EOSC Federation Handbook). The discussion yielded three priorities:

- There is a need for well-defined protocols and standards (ideally those supporting model technologies like RDF, SPARQL/GraphQL, RO-Crates, profiles), which is feasible in the short term; define not only minimal requirements but also the preferred long-term supported protocols and standards, to move towards a globally interoperable system;
- Raise awareness of European standards in the medium term: e.g. DCAT-AP obligation, SIMPL protocols; implement DataCite-compatible DCAT-AP (EOSC Academy can facilitate);
- Enhance awareness and use of existing services and resources (continuously).

If implemented, these suggestions would yield the following impact in facilitating the onboarding of resources to the EOSC Federation by

- enabling smooth connections across diverse systems, including those needed to populate the Federation with data and other Digital Objects, like DMPs, ELNs, Workflows, HPC, repositories;
- stabilising and aligning the EOSC Federation with the European Dataspaces.

The following needs were identified:

- Propagate activities from the EU or thematic Nodes to the national level (e.g. for reporting);
- Meta-repositories; onboarded services and resources must be evaluated;
- Repositories for ML models and container images (large models currently cannot be accommodated).

The **round table on long-term data retention** identified a single priority: Repositories onboarded in the Federation must have clear retention and preservation services. This is feasible in the short-term if Nodes ask services to fill in preservation plans. This would allow users of data to trust how and for how long data will be preserved, and would enhance transparency. The sustainability of repositories depends on Digital Objects having clearly defined retention periods, to enable deletion if necessary. It is at present unclear whether it should be upon the EOSC Nodes to enable this.

Thematic Track 2 closed with a list of miscellaneous gaps and challenges identified across the three round table discussions:

- Classifying protection level of onboarding services
- Data Sovereignty vs Digital Objects Sovereignty vs System Sovereignty
- Digital repatriation
- Other regulations beyond EU's might need to be considered
- CARE principles
- Awareness of the dependencies within the system at the node and federation levels
- Lack of business models

The discussion found that implementation is very domain specific, especially when it comes to validation services. Even a simple general data quality validation system would take years to set

up. Concerning the target group for data quality challenges, Mr Schubert said that reputation is relevant across the board, but that data quality issues ultimately have to be addressed by practitioners (i.e. the issue of data quality is always specific and concrete). With respect to data quality peer review, the group agreed that reporting can solve some of the current issues, however data quality reports need to be communicated transparently.

Data quality has two levels: 1) research processes and study design, and 2) data preservation; however, other aspects should be reported as well, e.g. whether data have been peer-reviewed. Data quality should be addressed at the service level and (data sources), as well as the level of data registries. Data registries already have many of the desired data quality features, even if the existence of detailed reporting does not (yet) imply high-quality data (similar to how FAIR does not imply high-quality research outputs). In that sense, it would be helpful to start from what data repositories are already offering, to then understand what communities implement with respect to data quality, to map out what already exists (accounting for different levels of maturity of standards, however).

Discussions highlighted the absence of clearly articulated sustainability and business models for the EOSC Federation. While Nodes currently rely largely on in-kind contributions and project-based funding, long-term sustainability will require structured funding mechanisms, defined cost-sharing models, and incentives for continued service provision. Participants noted the importance of aligning this work with forthcoming INFRA-2027 calls addressing business models and valorisation. Clarifying sustainability pathways is essential to ensure that operational growth does not outpace financial viability.

4.2.3 Thematic Track 3 – Competencies and Training

The aim of Thematic Track 3 on Competencies and Training was to bring together a wide range of stakeholders in the EOSC skills and training ecosystem to assess the current landscape and together define next steps to develop an EOSC skills and training roadmap. The session brought together around 40 participants including representatives from EOSC Nodes, competence centres, research infrastructures, projects, training providers and EOSC policy developers.

Helen Clare (Jisc) presented Thematic Track 3 results and stressed that the human element is an underrated challenge in implementing EOSC. The EOSC Academy is a good opportunity to enhance this aspect. In Session A, participants discussed the role of the EOSC Academy in the Federation, and made suggestions for its design and aims based on lessons learned from the EOSC Nodes. Session B addressed Embedding Training and Engagement in the Federation, clarifying synergies between Competence Centres, other training providers, and EOSC Nodes, and explored options to improve discovery of training material and catalogues. Session C consolidated previous recommendations from Sessions A and B and created a priority list of next steps for different stakeholders, with the goal of drafting a mandate for a new Working Group on Competences and Training. In this, the following key actors were identified: Institutes, Competence Centres, Research Infrastructures, Training Providers, EOSC projects with a training component, national bodies/projects involved in OS policies implementation, the EOSC Academy, the EOSC Nodes (i.e. people in the Nodes responsible for training), and research funders.

The recommendations from a report of the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group on *Digital skills for FAIR and open science*¹⁰ were recalled emphasising that the discussion on skills in EOSC is not new and, in fact, needs to build upon previous results. The discussions considered how the actors in skills and training should take part in addressing key themes: the role of the EOSC Academy and Competence Centres in the EOSC Federation, training material discovery and catalogues, and the mandate for a new Working Group.

Session A, organised by Isabel Caetano (EOSC-A, EOSC Gravity), Eleni Toli (Athena RC, EOSC Gravity), and Natalia Galica (NCN, EOSC Gravity), and chaired by Kamran Naim (EOSC-A), explored the role of the EOSC Academy, which is currently being developed by the EOSC Gravity project. The presentations from different types of Nodes (a national Node, a thematic Node, and the EOSC EU Node) identified several challenges, including limited IT and operational capacity, complex service and data onboarding, fragmented training resources, and a need for sustained user engagement. The session resulted in a list of potential topics for the EOSC Academy:

- Best practices, Success stories
- Use cases, Lessons learned, Case studies
- Tailored materials for Nodes (including Candidate Nodes) and service providers
- Workflow to become service provider
- Legal templates, licensing models, guidelines
- Material explaining EOSC and the EOSC Federation (also for sharing)

Participants suggested that these topics could be addressed in webinars and on-site workshops, but they also highlighted the important role mentoring and peer learning activities can play.

In terms of addressing the training needs of emerging Nodes, the needs of stakeholders (including all Nodes and service providers) must be understood and assessed, taking into account the various stages and roles and cluster material accordingly. A roadmap to onboard services in a Node (general information and Node-customised information), and a matchmaking mechanism (to be discussed if this should be done via the Federation or the Academy) should be created.

This resulted in a list of next steps:

- Maintain regular interaction with the EOSC Federation Training Working Group
- Make a needs assessment with relevant stakeholders (e.g. a survey)
- Create, collect, aggregate and curate relevant training resources
- Design and launch a series of webinars and targeted training actions
- Support cascading grant selected organisations/consortia by facilitating tailored learning opportunities
- Develop a dedicated microsite, as a space for sharing and providing access to all relevant information

Session B focused on the Role of Competence Centres (CCs), and was organized by Emma Lazzeri (CNR), Friederike Schmidt-Tremmel (Trust-IT, OSCARS) and Sara Di Giorgio (GARR).

¹⁰ European Commission DG RTD and EOSC Executive Board, *Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*, Barker, M. et al. (editors), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>.

There were presentations from Oliver Knodel (PaNOSC), Gilles Matthieu (Recherche Data Gouv), and Emma Lazzeri followed by **a world-café discussion to clarify the role of the EOSC Academy (which serves the Nodes) relative to the Competence Centres (which serve end users)**. Science communication officers in the EOSC Nodes would be needed to build bridges between communities and roles, and the unique technical skills of data stewards should be exploited, by redirecting questions to the right people. Domain-specific CCs that can support domain-specific work are key to achieve this. Currently, CCs miss the ability to facilitate, coordinate, and inform local communities. CCs can furthermore help identify the needs of researchers and users.

EOSC Nodes need to recognise the role of skills & competence managers, possibly by adding them to the list of people to be named by the Nodes. Potential roles in CCs include trainers, skilled personnel/experts (data stewards, data curators, etc.), training resource providers, authority / link to governance, event organisers, community managers, operational coordinators, and quality managers. The latter are needed to provide a common methodology and quality assurance for training resources.

It was concluded that each EOSC Node should have a CC-like function together with the IT infrastructure and services. The CC “function” should offer training on skills for Open Science, and for using the Node’s tools & services (which is not the same as a helpdesk). CCs without a link to an EOSC Node should be linked to the Federation for skills and competence matters.

The **round table on training material catalogues and discovery** discussed several topics that in their view should be included in the EOSC Federation Handbook: the sustainability of training materials, the importance of curation, the need to differentiate between resource and training catalogues, the desired flexibility of the system depending on the target community, the need to match the content to the needs of different communities, and the need to use global methodologies (train the trainer, FAIR-by-design).

To ensure training is findable, it was suggested that multiple platforms should “converge” on a central point where all resources should be accessible, but not necessarily in a single catalogue. In order to realise this, a minimal set of metadata for training resources is needed: training resources must be approached as any other resource, like e.g. data, and include versioning, curation, and possible rating systems.

Session C, organized by Celia van Gelder (Health-RI), Helen Clare (Jisc) and Isabel Caetano (EOSC-A, EOSC Gravity), aimed at developing an EOSC skills and training roadmap, by consolidating previous recommendations and those from Sessions A and B, as well as identifying and prioritising next steps for different stakeholder groups.

A main focus was the **discussion centered on drafting a mandate for a Training Working Group** under the new structure defined in the EOSC Federation MoU. In the period before the Winter School all Nodes were contacted and the majority expressed interest in supporting and contributing to formulate the WG and its mandate; however, no formal commitment was requested at that time. The discussion in Session C focused on the mandate and how the new Working Group will contribute to the Federation in 2026 as it transitions to production by formulating suitable deliverables. The objectives of the WG are as follows:

- To improve the integration of skills and training in the EOSC Federation;

- To define and promote the ecosystem of training for the EOSC Federation;
- To provide contributions to the EOSC Academy, CCs, and the Users Forum.

The expected outputs of the working group (2026) have been defined as follows:

- A minimal metadata schema for training (events/materials/methodology);
- A pilot for metadata transfer from sources like catalogue/registry/website into the EOSC EU Node catalogue;
- Define competencies and training requirements for EOSC Nodes and services in the EOSC Handbook;
- A model of the structure and integration of competences and skills in EOSC Nodes and Federation

The Working Group is foreseen to include training specialists from the Nodes and liaisons or guests from OAE5, Competence Centres, and relevant EOSC projects. After the Winter School, OAE5 will finalise the mandate with all contributing Nodes and present it to the Node Coordinators Committee for approval. At least 5 Nodes must be willing to participate in the Working Group for it to be formed.

Helen's final thoughts were dedicated to OAE5's position and remit in the EOSC ecosystem. OAE5 has identified key topics and organised its members several "work streams": CCs, Training Catalogues, Rewards & Recognition, Strategy & Engagement (in collaboration with EOSC Focus/Gravity). The Training and Competencies WG will help to further position and scope OAE5 activities and is expected to work on the Training Catalogue. In the coming period, OAE5 will revisit its scope and objectives, and also explore establishing a Task Force on skills & training.

In the discussion that followed, participants asked for clarification of the role of CCs in the Handbook, the availability of training materials in the Federation, and the place of trainers in the Federation. Helen stressed that training should be regarded as an aspect of sustainability for the Nodes and for the Federation; CCs will host training sessions on using services offered by the Nodes, thus adding to the information available via the Handbook. OAE2 offered its support to make educational materials machine-actionable by adding metadata, but the decision to have dedicated trainers must be solved by the EOSC Nodes.

5 Closing Session: Key outcomes, recommendations and the way forward

The closing session, chaired by EOSC-A president Klaus Tochtermann, comprised two parts: Part 1 recapped the Brokerage Event, including lessons learned; and part 2 included a panel discussion with representatives from all the groups that took part in the Winter School (i.e. EOSC Nodes, Thematic Tracks, EOSC Federation Build-up Group, and the EC) to gather high-level feedback on the Winter School, including the closed meeting of the Federation Build-up Group, as well as the Brokerage Event besides the “core” Winter School.

Part 1 was presented by Monika Gorál-Kurbiel (NCN) and Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT), who emphasised the great engagement and dedication shown by all participants in the event, reflected in the high number of attendees and meetings.

In the feedback received, participants stressed that the profiles in b2match were essential for the matchmaking, as there was such a large number of attendees/organisations to choose from. In future similar events, organisers should make profiles mandatory.

One of the most salient outcomes, and a testament to the success of the Brokerage Event, are the follow-up activities that have been confirmed by participants, such as

- onboarding services to your nodes, into a node
- Services integration, and connection among service
- training
- feedback on nodes: nodes received feedback on their approach and services effort
- joint efforts for future project proposals

Part 2 of the closing session featured a panel discussion on lessons learned from the Winter School, the Brokerage Event, and the Build-up Group meeting. In what follows, the most salient outcomes are reported. The panel included Klaus Tochtermann as moderator, with Bob Jones (EOSC-A, representing the EOSC Federation Build-up Group), Ana Teresa Mota (EC), Tibor Kálmán (GWDG, OAEG 1 co-coordinator) representing Thematic Track 1, Marek Cebecauer (Heyrovsky Institute, OAEG 1) representing Thematic Track 2, Celia van Gelder (Health-RI, OAEG 5) representing Thematic Track 3, Yann LeFranc (EUDAT), and Oliver Knodel (PaNOSC).

Figure 6: Closing Plenary.

Left to right: Oliver Knodel (PaNOSC), Yann LeFranc (EUDAT), Celia van Gelder (Health-RI, Thematic Track 3), Marek Cebecauer (OAEG1, Thematic Track 2), Tibor Kalman (OAEG1, Thematic Track 1), Ana Teresa Mota (EC), Bob Jones (EOSC-A, CERN), Klaus Tochtermann (EOSC-A, ZBW).

Panellists opened the discussion stating what they saw as the most salient aspect of the Winter School. Bob Jones mentioned the value of bringing together individuals and organisations working on the Federation with people from INFRAEOSC projects to reduce silos and barriers. Ana Teresa Mota highlighted the commitment in the EOSC community to build a common understanding from so many sources; enabled by the common space created by the Winter School. For Tibor Kálmán, the very intense four days managed to break communication silos; the input and discussions now need to be digested and brought back to the OAEGs to be turned into concrete actions. Marek Cebecauer was impressed by the will to contribute in kind to bringing the EOSC Federation to life, and by the dedication to bring back to the table the topics of the OAEGs after being side-lined during 2025. For Celia van Gelder, the number of collaboration opportunities that surfaced, especially for OAEG5, stood out. There is a clear growing interest from other EOSC stakeholders for the topic of skills and training. Yann LeFranc, on behalf of the EOSC Nodes, said that it was now clear that the Nodes had to re-connect with the EOSC expert pool (OAEGs and Task Forces), and become familiarised with what they and EOSC-related projects have achieved. He also emphasised that the Nodes should be more in touch with experts to work towards the EOSC Federation. Oliver Knodel stressed that the Brokerage Event provided a good opportunity to engage with the EOSC community, develop ideas for services to integrate into PaNOSC, and to devise a strategy for 2026. Klaus Tochtermann stressed the nature of EOSC as a socio-technical infrastructure as evidenced by the lively EOSC community around all other technical aspects.

Thematic Track representatives identified the two key priorities that emerged from the Winter School. For Track 1, the key priority is to identify and make transparent which existing trusted bodies can endorse the decision-making in EOSC. The second priority concerns creating clear

links between the various existing structures; for instance, while the Build-up Group is focused on creating EOSC, OAEGs said that they would be better able to represent the user perspective.

For Thematic Track 2, the top priority is the need to understand what is meant by data quality and data control, what standards and protocols are needed to understand where we want to go, and a vision for the future. In the short term, resource providers and repositories should be asked to put preservation policies in place, and clear decision-making structures, including communication channels and training, should be established.

The first priority for Track 3 is to make training resources findable in the Federation, for which the Training Working Group will be instrumental. Competence Centres should be made a core functionality of EOSC Nodes, and OAEG5 could help in defining a suitable model to include skills and training in the structure of the Nodes.

Bob Jones indicated that the decision-making processes in the Federation will be established using the governance structure described in the MoU, which foresees having a separate operational committee for technical matters.

With respect to communication between structures, co-locating the Build-up Group meeting with the Winter School has proven very effective. Mr Jones was very supportive of the recommendations from Track 3 regarding the potential role of Competence Centres. Regarding data quality, he emphasised that reputation is key, but that ultimately it should be organisations (and not individual researchers) who should be responsible.

Mr Jones remarked that the Build-up Group relies on the work of EOSC-A TFs, but a discussion is needed about how to deploy results and the selection of appropriate standards. He urged EOSC-A expert groups to access the Federation to see what is available now and understand what the deployment of results would entail. Regarding preservation strategies by EOSC Nodes, he reminded the audience that project charters are expected to talk about the sustainability of the Nodes, ideally going beyond two years, and the same should hold for data quality challenges.

Mr Tochtermann added that aligning decision-making processes is central to advance the Federation, and that a balance must be found between top-down and bottom-up approaches. From the EUDAT Node's perspective, Mr Le Franc reported that balanced decision-making is a challenge for them given their relatively large number of members (23 at present), which puts a lot of strain as interests do not always converge. In their experience, the top difficulty is defining boundaries between decision-making layers. How to reach consensus is another sticky point, as it requires a delicate balance of power, and should ideally evolve in the Federation together with the Nodes. He stressed that the current decision-making processes do not reflect the links with INFRAEOSC projects or EOSC expert groups, and that projects should strive to contribute. From the perspective of a disciplinary Node, Mr Knodel added that PaNOSC, formed by large-scale infrastructures, deals with large amounts of research data kept in different repositories, and that the integration process of the repositories in the EOSC Catalogue has now been clarified and needs now to be properly documented.

Ms Mota emphasised that the Federation must agree on the standards to be implemented. Monitoring of Federating Capabilities needs to be in place to assess service quality and track usage. EOSC is embedded in the strategy of the EU and is kept as a top priority in the ERA agenda as its appearance in early drafts of FP10 shows. The Federation could become the most widely

used research infrastructure in the EU if developed properly. Ms Mota promised to transmit the commitment perceived in the EOSC community to her team, together with the motivation found in the Winter School to solve problems, the will to prepare the ground for new EOSC Nodes, and the need to ensure effective decision-making processes in the new governance structure. This was noted by Mr Jones as forming a very good basis for the continuation of EOSC as a partnership in FP10.

6 Lessons learned and conclusion

With its third edition, the EOSC Winter School has once more proven itself as a key event for the EOSC community, bringing together experts from all over Europe for in-depth discussions, strategic dialogue, networking, and first-hand insights into the latest developments of the EOSC Federation. Under the motto *“Supporting the EOSC Federation”*, the Winter School fostered convergence across the diverse EOSC stakeholders through:

- Enabling dialogue and mutual learning between EOSC Nodes and the wider EOSC community to support future applications and resource onboarding
- Providing structured opportunities for networking and alliance-building
- Enhancing collaboration through in-depth thematic discussions and hands-on working sessions

Building on the substantial progress achieved by the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, the EOSC Winter School 2026 further advanced convergence on the EOSC Federation among all stakeholders, by co-locating the Winter School with a (closed) meeting of the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, as well as introducing a new format for mutual exchange and learning. The co-location of the Build-up Group meeting with the Winter School proved highly effective in strengthening communication among diverse EOSC stakeholders and in bringing the EOSC-A expert groups into closer alignment with ongoing EOSC Federation developments.

With broad representation across Europe, the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event has proven effective in facilitating direct contact between service providers and EOSC Federation Nodes and supporting the practical build-up of the EOSC Federation. Participants reported that the event was highly relevant, enabling them to learn about available products and services, initiate onboarding processes for their Node(s) or service(s), establish valuable connections, and lay the groundwork for continued collaboration beyond the event. Overall, the EOSC Stakeholder Brokerage Event can be considered a successful pilot format that effectively supports the operationalisation of the EOSC Federation. The experience gained in Nice provides a strong foundation for refining and replicating this format in future EOSC events.

Building on the strategic priorities identified by the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, the three Thematic Tracks examined key gaps and challenges across three core areas: (i) clarifying the role of the EOSC EU Node within the Federation; (ii) refining and strengthening the Federation’s governance structure; and (iii) defining and aligning federating capabilities. Through collaborative analysis and structured discussion, the Tracks aimed to identify viable solutions and synthesise recommendations for consideration by the EOSC Federation Build-up Group.

The Thematic Tracks identified the following key priorities: For Thematic Track 1, the key priority is to identify trusted bodies that can endorse the decision-making in EOSC. The second priority concerns creating clear links between the various existing structures; for instance, while the Build-up Group is focused on creating EOSC, OAEGs said that they could better represent the user perspective. For Thematic Track 2, the key priority is the need to understand and better define data quality and data control, as well as the standards and protocols needed to understand where the Federation should evolve (i.e., a vision for the future). Further, resource providers and repositories should be asked to put preservation policies in place and establish

clear decision-making structures, including communication channels and training. For Thematic Track 3, the key priority is to make training resources findable in the Federation, for which the Training Working Group will be instrumental; second, Competence Centres should be made a core functionality of EOSC Nodes, and OAEG5 could help in defining a suitable model to include skills and training in the structure of the Nodes.

Overall, feedback from participants on the EOSC Winter School 2026, collected through multiple channels, including direct verbal input and Mentimeter responses, was very positive and reflected a high level of engagement with both the content and the format of the event. Thematic Tracks were praised for their clear structure and their ability to enable focused and productive discussions. The only notable criticism concerned group size, especially within the “Federating Capabilities and Interoperability” track, which attracted a disproportionately high number of participants and may have benefited from being divided into separate sessions. Participants also commended the overall preparation of the event and especially valued hands-on discussions, concrete examples, and national perspectives. Frequently used one-word descriptions included “intensive,” “inspiring,” “useful,” “engaging,” “valuable,” “strategic,” “future-oriented,” “relevant,” “interactive,” and “collaborative.” For future editions, respondents recommended maintaining the current format, particularly the combination of lightning talks and hands-on sessions, as well as the Stakeholder Brokerage Event. They also suggested more direct involvement of prospective end users (researchers) and earlier communication of session details to support better preparation.

In all of this, the EOSC Winter School 2026 significantly deepened collaboration across the wider EOSC community and strengthened alignment with the EOSC Federation Build-up Group. A fourth edition of the EOSC Winter School is planned for early 2027, with the support of the EOSC Gravity project.

7 Annex I: Detailed description of Thematic Track Sessions (28 January 2026)

7.1 Thematic Track 1 – Federating Capabilities and Interoperability

7.1.1 Introduction to Interoperability in the EOSC Federation

This session included lightning talks from several INFRAEOSC projects (EOSC Beyond, EOSC DataCommons, OSTrails), the Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF, and the EOSC Federation Subgroup on Cybersecurity and Incident Handling.

Figure 7: Impressions from Thematic Track 1.

The focus of this session, chaired by Diego Scardaci (EGI/EOSC Beyond) and Jiří Marek (CESNET/EOSC Beyond), was interoperability. The chairs set the scene with a presentation on the EOSC Architecture and current status of interoperability. The vision of the EOSC Federation as a network of federated autonomous nodes of different types (national, regional, thematic, e-infrastructure) is built upon a reference model for individual nodes that comprises core capabilities like AAI and helpdesks along generic resource provisioning, “glued” by a set of Federating Capabilities. As of now, only AAI and resource catalogues are mandatory, with other federating capabilities to be added during 2026. Central to this transition is the update of the EOSC Interoperability Framework, which seeks to shift from human-readable guidelines to machine-composable resources through new configuration templates and a revamped registry. Ongoing work, also by projects like EOSC United and EOSC Beyond, is currently refining these standards to ensure technical, semantic, legal, and organisational alignment across the Federation.

7.1.2 Thematic Track 1 Session A – Identifying Solutions

7.1.2.1 An introduction to FAIR Implementation Profiles (Alexandra Kokkinaki, Barbara Magagna, Wolmar N. Åkerström)

FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) are machine-readable collections of choices made by a community of practice to operationalise the FAIR Principles. FIPs foster a shared technology stack and accelerating convergence and reuse across scientific domains. The FIP ecosystem is rapidly expanding, with nearly 1,000 published profiles and over 1,300 FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs) integrated into tools like the FIP Wizard and FAIR Connect. The FIPs have the following benefits:

- FIPs help to put FAIR into practice and support explicit community decisions
- FIPs accelerate convergence by reusing trusted FSR
- FIPs enable harmonisation by providing a shared language and tech stack
- FIPs enable machine-readable/scalable resource reuse in DMPs
- FIPs can be used for documentation, but also for recommendations; allow user-friendly curation collaboratively, aligned with the FAIR guiding principles
- FIPs/FAIRsharing resources should be machine-readable

FIPs are a promising tool for EOSC, e.g. to create profiles per EOSC Nodes, resource catalogues, and recommending FSRs in EOSC.

7.1.2.2 The maDMP Interoperability Framework (Tomasz Miksa)

The Data Management Plan Interoperability Framework (DMP-IF) developed in the OSTrails project, aims to modernise research planning by shifting DMPs from static documents to machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs). The DMP-IF serves as the "glue" between various RDM services, including DMP platforms, repositories, Scientific Knowledge Graphs, and FAIR assessment tools. By using the RDA DMP Common Standard and a common maDMP API, the Framework enables automated metadata exchange, to find research results from repositories, or evaluate FAIRness of DMPs. The Framework is designed to prevent vendor lock-in and enhance the transparency and traceability of the research lifecycle through integrated planning, tracking, and assessment pathways.

7.1.2.3 Demonstrating cross-domain Essential Climate Variable data access using harmonisation at the data level (Tjerk Krijger)

The ENVRI-Hub NEXT project aims to harmonise data from diverse Research Infrastructures to enable accessing and comparing Essential Climate Variable (ECV) data. Since individual RIs use different APIs, metadata models, and vocabularies, researchers find it difficult to use cross-domain data in Virtual Research Environments. To solve this, the project employs the I-ADOPT ontology as a semantic broker to decompose targeted variables and map them to a standardized SKOS vocabulary on the NERC Vocabulary Server. This allows users to make generic data requests via Python notebooks (specifying an ECV, time range, and bounding box) which automatically map to relevant RI-specific parameters. The project further aims to improve

cross-domain access by establishing a data lake to return single, harmonised files that exactly match user queries, rather than providing multiple RI-specific datasets.

7.1.2.4 FDOs: Semantic Interoperability in the EOSC Federation - The EOSC DataCommons Approach (Lukasz Opiola, Enol Fernández)

The EOSC DataCommons project aims to bridge data repositories with execution environments to facilitate FAIR and reproducible research across EOSC as the European Research Commons. At the heart of its technical approach is the Request Package, a hybrid interoperability solution that uses RO-Crate for semantic linking and machine-actionable metadata, and BagIt for reliable data transfers and fixity. This architecture allows users to define complex data processing jobs (including tool specifications like Galaxy workflows and references to remote data via specific protocols) in a standardised, FAIR Digital Object. Scheduled for full implementation by early 2028, the project seeks to have the Request Package adopted in the EOSC Interoperability Framework, creating a "snowball effect" where any participating repository or execution environment becomes inherently interoperable with the existing network.

7.1.2.5 Metadata inconsistencies and interoperability: impact on data discovery (Nicola Fiore)

EOSC Beyond highlighted how metadata heterogeneity (encompassing structural, semantic, and syntactic differences) leads to fragmented and unreliable data discovery. To address this, the project advocates for a Semantic Framework rather than a single fixed standard, using a top-level ontology for alignment and tools like VocBench for shared vocabulary management. Central to this approach is the EOSC Integration Suite (EOSC IS), which transforms heterogeneous metadata into interoperable resources through the use of adapters and semantic alignment. This provides a lifecycle for the adapters, allowing providers to onboard, verify, and share them via a registry, and has already been populated with 10 core and 15 horizontal adapters across 8 pilot nodes.

7.1.2.6 Harmonising and integrating (meta)data from various sources (Paolo Manghi, Daniel Garijo)

To enable unified search and analytics, the project employs interoperability guidelines that define common APIs, core data models, exchange formats, and cross-walks for translating diverse datasets into a standardised structure. These efforts support the EOSC EU Node's Federating Capabilities, which include metadata harvesting and data engineering to maintain a registry of data sources governed by specific content acquisition, data quality, and Quality of Service policies. Practical applications of these guidelines are seen in initiatives like OSTrails for scientific knowledge graphs and FAIR tools, EOSC Beyond for federated search, and Software Heritage for software-specific metadata.

7.1.2.7 Federating Capabilities and Interoperability: How to deal with a diversity of solutions (Esteban González)

This presentation identified critical gaps and provided recommendations for new Federating Capabilities based on an analysis of use cases from Life Sciences and Astronomy. The study

highlights significant obstacles to seamless collaboration, including fragmented AAI mechanisms, inconsistent metadata practices, and incompatible ontologies. To address these issues, it is recommended to establish "Radical Transparency" through shared rules for digital assets, enabling machine-composable services, and implementing federated compute and storage to bring analysis closer to the data. Leveraging AI tools and specialised metadata schemes like CroissantML and FAIR4ML can help to automate and enhance interoperability. The EOSC IF has been drafted for humans, but more work is needed to target machines.

The Technical Interoperability TF has collected 82 use cases and 70 user stories from different domains (including Life Sciences, Photon and Neutron, Astronomy and Astrophysics). From them, it has identified technical needs (metadata management, data sharing practices, and service integration), gaps (inconsistent metadata and APIs, incompatible formats, limited access to resources, insufficient training, missing data and service policies). The TF recommends new Federating Capabilities that enable easy "consumability" of resources by AI (i.e. machine-readable), and interoperability guidelines that can be used by machines.

7.1.2.8 Challenges to service discovery and interoperability (Kostas Koumantaros)

This presentation details a significant architectural shift from a centralised hub-and-spoke model to a decentralised, federated network of autonomous EOSC Nodes. Central to this new infrastructure is the EOSC Node Registry, which acts as a global "address book" allowing nodes to discover each other, look up endpoints, and exchange metadata about their specific technical capabilities. This approach is exemplified by the Federated Search use case, where a researcher can query resources across multiple nodes simultaneously through an integrated system of front offices, resource catalogues, and messaging services. By providing PIDs and machine-readable endpoints for nodes like NI4OS and CESSDA, the framework aims to ensure global inclusiveness and interoperability across EOSC.

7.1.2.9 EOSC-specific incident handling/mitigation (Urpo Kaila)

This presentation outlined the framework for incident handling and mitigation. Cybersecurity has been elevated to a mandatory requirement by elevated risk perception and new regulations like NIS2 and the Cyber Resilience Act, leading to the establishment of a formal EOSC cybersecurity policy and a dedicated CSIRT service. For EOSC Nodes, the Handbook mandates appointing a Cybersecurity Officer, maintaining a prompt incident response capability, and reporting major threats to a centralised security contact. A practical incident handling checklist emphasised professional conduct, stakeholder communication, evidence preservation through forensic procedures, and the continuous improvement of security measures based on lessons learned as key ingredients to improve cybersecurity.

7.1.2.10 Thematic Track 1 Session A – Q&A and Discussion

At present, resources in the EOSC common catalogue are described adopting recommendations from the community developed over the years, starting from core standards and protocols used by major platforms. The EOSC EU Node platform is currently being adapted to the emerging needs of the EOSC Federation, and new projects are investigating new ways to make schemas interoperable by e.g. AI-based interpretation of metadata. The main concern was

the sustainability of project outcomes. In the remaining time, participants shortlisted available opportunities to make concrete recommendations to the Federation. Since many services are outcomes of EOSC-related projects, a discussion is needed on how these services can be made sustainable when projects end.

7.1.3 Session B – Analysing Solutions

To increase interaction among participants, the Subcommittee organised six round tables to discuss as many topics in three consecutive discussion rounds. Session chairs prepared brief input on their respective topics in advance, delivered as short presentations. The discussion was facilitated by “prompts”, also prepared in advance, shared with participants via shared documents. On average, each table seated about 20 participants per round.

7.1.3.1 Resource categorisation in the EOSC Federation and resource profiles - state of the art (Chair: Roksana Wilk)

The discussion noted that while the EOSC EU Node uses currently specific resource models and service categories to deliver and annotate tools for research, these are not yet formally adopted as Federation-wide standards. The primary goals of this initiative are to evaluate community support for these outputs, propose enhancements, and collect data on the diverse categorisation models used by EOSC nodes. Initial conclusions suggest that while existing models are considered a strong starting point for official standardisation, further input must be gathered from stakeholders to refine these frameworks.

7.1.3.2 Adoption of FAIR Implementation Profiles in Projects, User Communities and EOSC Services (Chairs: Barbara Magagna, Wolmar N. Åkerström)

This round table focused on adopting FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) to document technical and policy choices across projects, user communities, and EOSC services. A FIP serves as a curated collection of technical implementation choices made by a community of practice for each FAIR principle, specifically referencing FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs) such as identifier services, metadata schemas, and data usage licenses. To date, there exist around 1000 FIPs, which together reference 1300+ FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs), registered in databases such as FAIRsharing. The round table discussion yielded the following recommendations:

It was suggested to promote registering all key (EOSC) interoperability (framework) solutions in databases (e.g. FAIRsharing) to be referenced as recommended FSRs, linking them to the specific gaps in FAIR implementation they can address. Further, it was agreed that FIPs can have a role in EOSC, in terms of declaring, sharing, and comparing implementation choices to support landscaping, convergence and mediation (which FSRs are used where, for what, and how widely). A strategy for promoting FIPs in EOSC would involve identifying relevant federating use cases to form agreement on appropriate granularity and specificity required for FIPs to support automated composability, assessment, and mediation.

7.1.3.3 Realising Semantic Interoperability with FDOs in EOSC (Chair: Esteban González)

This table focused on how to achieve semantic interoperability through FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) in the EOSC Federation. The project identifies several implementations of FDOs, highlighting PID-based approaches, RO-Crates, and nanopublications, with the FDO-Forum currently defining "supported" flavours for these technologies. Key challenges include implementing cross-platform FDO operations such as format conversion via discovery services, and ensuring interoperability between machine-actionable RO-Crate profiles. Ultimately, the goal is to standardise these interoperability solutions using a shared set of evaluation criteria to support the broader federated infrastructure.

7.1.3.4 Service Discovery and Interoperability EOSC-specific incident handling and mitigation (Chairs: Kostas Koumantaros, Urpo Kaila)

This table focused on the EOSC Federation's strategy for service discovery and incident handling, emphasising the urgent need for a robust cybersecurity policy in response to evolving regulations like NIS2 and the Cyber Resilience Act. To manage risks across distributed nodes, it has been proposed to establish an EOSC CSIRT (Computer Security Incident Response Team) and a unified security framework leveraging standards such as ISO/IEC 27001, FitSM, and SIRTFI 2.0. The document outlines requirements for EOSC Nodes, including the appointment of cybersecurity officers and adherence to a structured incident handling checklist focused on evidence security, damage containment, and stakeholder notification. Additionally, it advocates for machine-actionable standardised metadata to enhance service discovery and building trust through service classification based on operational maturity and security best practices.

7.1.3.5 Metadata quality harmonisation and Integration (Chairs: Paolo Manghi, Alexandra Kokkinaki)

This table focused on metadata quality, harmonisation, and integration across scientific domains. It establishes a comprehensive framework where quality is assessed through standardized flags, scientific rigour, and AI-assisted enrichment. Harmonisation is achieved by employing controlled vocabularies, officially endorsed mappings, and common schemas like NeXus to enable cross-domain research, while integration focuses on using PIDs and virtual collection registries to streamline discovery. The document synthesizes these efforts into universal success factors—highlighting community adoption, automation, and training—to ensure that federated resources remain scientifically trustworthy, technically interoperable, and scalable.

7.1.3.6 Federating Services & Technical Interoperability (Chair: Diego Scardaci)

This table identified critical gaps in the current EOSC Federating Capabilities and proposed essential technical solutions for a more integrated Federation. Key priorities include the development of clear implementation guidelines for Nodes to enable federated search via standardised APIs, and the creation of a real semantic federation that aligns vocabularies and knowledge graphs to facilitate cross-node queries. The group emphasised the need for machine-actionable resources across services, a unified security and cybersecurity framework, and a standardised Node registry to dynamically identify service providers. Ultimately, these

enhancements aim to shift the federation’s focus toward more robust support for complex scientific workflows and cross-node data usage.

7.1.4 Session C – Synthesising

In Thematic Track 1, session C was organized as a series of lightning talks to report back from the session B round tables, followed by a lively plenary discussion attempting to unify the threads laid out in the preceding sessions A and B. In what follows, the most salient results of the round tables are summarized, as reported by the round table chairs.

FIPs have been introduced as a tool for communities to describe their implementation choices with respect to the FAIR principles; suggestions on how to select candidate interop solutions for implementation (maturity level, practical applicability, usability, generality, formalisation, traceability); consider the appropriate level of specificity for a service that addresses a specific data type, plus what has been broadly adopted by others.

The round table on FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) introduced and discussed three competing implementation paradigms for FDOs: PID-based¹¹, RO-Crate¹², and nanopublications¹³. The first two “attach” information about a resource (location, usage details, provenance information, etc.) to the resource itself. Nanopublications are an alternative method to provide information about data (as central element of the whole scientific knowledge system) as a more direct way to enable a semantic web of data.

Figure 8: Lightning talk, Thematic Track 1, Session A.

¹¹ <https://fairdo.org/basic-fdo-definition/>

¹² <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹³ <https://nanopub.net/>

The session also featured inputs on cybersecurity, a topic tangential to interoperability, but equally fundamental to the EOSC Federation. Cybersecurity requires trust, so this needs to be understood in order to be achieved. In order for this to succeed, every Node needs to have a security officer, and in particular, move away from a business logic of (primarily) addressing end users to a logic of services addressing other services.

Round table 6 collected feedback to improve the models for Federating Capabilities presented, and define a list of actionable priorities:

- 1) Step-by-step interoperability guidelines for Nodes to implement Federating Capabilities
- 2) Define a real semantic federation
- 3) Define a federated data access
- 4) PID capabilities
- 5) Support for machine-actionable resources (FDOs) in all (core or federating) services
- 6) Cybersecurity across nodes is missing
- 7) Stronger focus on scientific use cases

The plenary discussion (moderated by Tibor Kálmán) aimed to reach a common understanding of the 2026 goals for interoperability, focusing on what users should be enabled to do, and what needs to be achieved for that, such as reviewing the Build-up Group's priorities regarding interoperability, as an indication of where the Federation sees itself by the end of 2026.

Others pointed out that adoption is the responsibility of EOSC Nodes, rather than of the EOSC expert groups represented at the WS. It is up to the Nodes to adopt and adapt solutions, but at present they do not seem able to exploit all the information coming out of the expert groups. The chances of this happening would improve if expert groups were able to make more concrete proposals, but limited resources and funding in the Nodes complicate the picture. OAEG2 should take these ideas and think what can be realistically done by the Nodes in order to establish their priorities for 2026. This should be done by also consulting EOSC-related projects, maybe involving Node coordinators in the discussions to avoid mismatching expectations. All involved should be aware that whatever is done will not satisfy all parties, and even the best solution might not be adopted because of limited resources, so it is important to manage expectations to avoid frustration among EOSC expert groups. Besides input from OAEGs, TFs, and projects, users should also be asked to establish the priorities.

Consensus emerged regarding the discovery of resources (and of data in particular) as the key priority. Fundamentally, the group agreed that digital objects need to be findable in the first place before researchers can do anything with them ("get the data first, and then ask questions on semantics"). A different approach is to distinguish between what is feasible for the Nodes from the most urgent challenge identified by the projects. Implementation guidelines are fundamental to have a federated system running by the end of 2026, which, requires well-defined APIs.

The list of priorities defined by Track 1 needs to be further broken down into addressable steps, e.g. quality criteria for datasets and inclusion of variable description in metadata. This might be hampered by the fact how groups discuss their topics differs from one another, and, moreover, the Federation has its own decision-making process independent of what the expert groups do, which makes it difficult to keep the momentum. A first step would be to add minimum standards to enable federated search. It might work better to start by building something smaller that can

be included in a Node as a “proof of concept” e.g. including protocols for mutual communications, and move on to Federating Capabilities later, as this will raise architectural questions. The decision-making bodies of the Federation can then decide on what to implement (based e.g. on scalability).

The session closed with a remark on the potential role of the wider EOSC community in this process. In particular, challenges to the Federation cannot be solved by solely addressing them from the vantage point of the Federation. An appropriate approach would be to start building solutions locally that can be implemented globally. This requires an open process where the Nodes assess what solutions are already out there. In other words, the community needs to make a decision about how it wants to proceed. Building task forces with different hats is the right approach, and EOSC-A is the right community for this.

7.2 Thematic Track 2: Resources

7.2.1 Session A – Identifying Solutions

Thematic Track 2 was organized around the broad topic of resources (services, tools, etc.) for the EOSC Federation. Session A was organized as lightning talks on selected topics. Session B was organized as three parallel World Cafe tables, each diving deeper on selected solutions presented in Session A. Specifically: i) data quality, ii) standards and specifications for services populating the EOSC Federation with data and FDOs, and iii) data retention and preservation. In Session C, table chairs summarised the table discussion outputs, followed by a plenary discussion to derive common recommendations to the EOSC Federation Build-up Group. The presentations introduced various approaches on how to integrate different resources with the EOSC Federation.

7.2.1.1 RO-Crates & ROHub platform (Daniel Garijo, Sebastián Luna-Valero)

Daniel Garijo described how all resources can be included in a Research Object, since everything can be described using metadata. RO-Crates collect in one place all information related to a given research output by adding metadata on related data, publications, workflows, authors, organisations, licences, etc. Moreover, ROHub¹⁴ and RO-Crates enable semantic enrichment, recommendations, comprehension, impact, research life cycle, completeness & FAIR assessment. The related project EOSC Data Commons¹⁵ plans to dynamically create RO-crates based on user input. Data, tools and services are aggregated in a unified web interface. Scientists in EOSC search for data assisted with AI-based technology. Once the data of interest is found, the EOSC Matchmaker¹⁶ will suggest tools and services to analyse the data. It is then up to the user to select a tool or service to process the data. Upon selection, the EOSC Matchmaker creates an RO-crate containing all the required information. This RO-Crate is then passed onto the EOSC Data Player¹⁷ which will inspect the content and execute the necessary

¹⁴ <https://www.rohub.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu/service/eosc-matchmaker>

¹⁷ <https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu/service/eosc-data-player>

actions to provide the user with an execution environment prepared with the requested data and software ready for experimenting.

7.2.1.2 Populating the EOSC Federation with Data: Electronic Lab Notebooks and workflows (Marek Cebecauer)

To add interoperable data in the EOSC Federation such that it enables discovery and reuse requires metadata to be added automatically, instead of manually like it is generally done now. Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs) can generate XML, JSON, and YAML files, and some systems even create RO-Crates, but interoperability cannot be guaranteed. ELNs and workflow orchestrators can help with adding metadata, especially in experimental research, but orchestrators are needed for workflows. At present, however, there is no quality control or assurance (QC/QA) in place, so any file that carries JSON etc. would be accepted, as there are no minimum requirements. QC/QA can be a problem with increased automation. SHACL can help, but human curation and annotation will not disappear soon. In the discussion it was pointed out that at present, ELNs differ across disciplines (even within institutions). SHACL does not make much sense if there is no agreement on semantics. Some disciplines (e.g. materials science) have made good progress with standardisation, but this is not the case with others (e.g. life sciences). It would help if W3C standards were used.

Figure 9: Lightning talk, Thematic Track 2.

7.2.1.3 Data Quality Knowledge Base of Standards Definitions (Chris Schubert)

Chris Schubert highlighted that the importance of data quality is generally underestimated, in particular as its understanding depends on one's position in the system. Alignment could be increased using an ISO standard (ISO 8000¹⁸) for data used in Machine Learning and analytics,

¹⁸ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:8000:-1:ed-1:v1:en>

which defines data quality as “conformance of [data] characteristics to requirements”. ISO has furthermore issued 8 different definitions of data quality “based on purposes, historical development and domain pillars”, and CODATA has issued similar definitions. The question is then whether something similar can be achieved for EOSC, e.g. through the establishment of a data quality knowledge base.

In the discussion, it was pointed out that quality is extremely difficult to define and it does not have the same meaning across disciplines. In e.g. biodiversity, “Fitness for use/purpose” has been introduced as a good quality measure, but this leaves little space for introducing data provenance.

7.2.1.4 Conceptual tool towards Long-Term Data Retention (Jacques Flores, Hervé L’Hours)

Jacques Flores talked about tools that can support repository managers in long-term data retention. The Retention, Reappraisal Iteration Logic tool (RRAIL) developed by the EOSC-A Long-Term Data Retention TF to this end aims to define a common terminology in long-term retention, follow a Digital Object as it moves through (re)appraisal and retention/reservation, and map recommendations from EOSC EDEN and EOSC FIDELIS on core preservation principles and activities and functions expected to be provided by repositories. RRAIL is dependent on the following 4 building blocks:

- Digital Object Characteristics
- Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attribute Matrix (TTRAM)
- Level of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)
- Core Preservation Processes (CPP, an outcome from EOSC EDEN)

The goal would be for all long-term repositories in the Federation to use RRAIL. TTRAM¹⁹ proposes a list of procedures/operations repositories should perform on the things they store. The idea is that data must be appraised and probably reappraised before they are deemed good for LTR. LoRCAP²⁰ establishes the levels of preservation achievable by repositories.

7.2.1.5 Overview of resources, services and architecture of the upcoming EHDS (Matthias Löbe, Wolmar N. Åkerström)

Matthias Löbe spoke about finding and using health data, a current discussion in the Health Data TF. This is a difficult problem due to the huge diversity of data types and stakeholders. The European Health Data Space (EHDS) should provide a solution to this problem. At present, a three-layered model to enable primary (e.g. access via EU) and secondary use (for research) of health data, and the establishment of Electronic Healthcare Records (HER) is under development. The EHDS regulation²¹ suggests how health data ecosystems may be organised

¹⁹ L’Hours, H. et al. (2025), *FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v01.00 Introduction and Overview (v01.00)*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144159>.

²⁰ L’Hours, H. et al. (2025), *FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v00.02 Guide (v00.02)*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15676189>.

²¹ https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space-regulation-ehds_en

in EU member states by using extensions of DCAT-AP²² (still to be developed in many cases). Since the EOSC Federation aims at allowing the sharing of health data, which is presently not possible in EHDS, differences with the EHDS regulation can be expected that will likely affect the industry.

7.2.1.6 EXTRACT-TASKA: A distributed workflow orchestrator for radio astronomy data processing (Baptiste Cecconi)

The EXTRACT project aims to create a data-mining platform for extreme data across the compute continuum, based on scientific (TASKA) and non-scientific (PER) use cases. TASKA is about combining and analysing astronomy data pertaining to a single observation stored in different locations to create images that enable research, ensuring that “where what is done” is transparent for users (although not all users need to see the rather complex technical foundations). EXTRACT will help the astrophysics community use distributed resources in EOSC to optimise resources. To avoid troubles (e.g. clogging the system), resources are assigned by a system layer that remains invisible to end users. Documentation under development will nevertheless enable interested scientists understand how that happens.

7.2.2 Session B – Analysing Solutions

Discussions were organised around three parallel round tables with three rotating topics, introduced by the respective chairs.

7.2.2.1 Table 1 - Classification and transparency on retention and active preservation of EOSC Nodes that retain/preserve data (Jacques Flores, Hervé L'Hours)

In the introduction, Jacques Flores suggested that all information about data retention and preservation must be stored in a Digital Object. This must be implemented in EOSC. Since infinite data retention is impossible to guarantee, all that can be achieved is for communities to indicate a point of data reappraisal, enabled through machine actionable policies. This requires repository managers to know well disciplinary practices, probably involving funders (via e.g. grant registries) who might have information about the discipline where datasets come from. This could become mandatory for repositories in the Federation, and would help services that use particular datasets by indicating e.g. how long data will be available.

UNIX has a built-in mechanism to indicate/track data usage that could be used with PIDs in an RO-Crate, which might avoid the need to copy them to ensure preservation. A similar mechanism might be used to trigger reappraisal. The group agreed that what must be preserved must be decided by data governance.

Metadata can deal with most of these challenges. Funders should be made aware about the value of data so that they push repositories to require certain characteristics of data/datasets to be stored as metadata, like information about preservation policies, which is important for anyone who access or reuses it. For repositories to be able to play this key role (lifting the

²² The DCAT Application Profile for data portals in Europe (DCAT-AP) is a specification based on the Data Catalogue (DCAT) vocabulary for describing public sector datasets in Europe. See: <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>

responsibility of communities and individual researchers), they need to have appropriate data preservation policies in place. Metadata thus enable preservation to be “outsourced” from data owners to repositories/data holders. In any case, funders retain a key role because it is them who determine the rules that institutions have to follow, probably according to national or EU-wide policies and licences, and therefore can strongly influence implementation.

In the end, balance must be sought between the requirements by scientific communities and those by funders. This can be achieved in various ways: repositories can use labels that indicate quality, like CoreTrustSeal, or they could be asked to meet certain criteria (without a full classification system), with procedures in place to allow them to fix non-compliance issues. This latter mechanism replaces fixing exclusion criteria with providing incentives for repository managers to reach certain standards (ideally, set by funders in accordance with community practices), thus establishing a procedure for those behind the curve to catch up.

This provides a direct link to sustainability: if funders set rules for repositories, they should also help them achieve those goals, maybe by relating the achievement of quality standards to helping them to become sustainable²³. Funder requests to add metadata have proven to constitute a push in the right direction for researchers to do things the right way.

Communities should be involved by e.g. clarifying to researchers the value of adopting community practices, including data reusing, which at present is much less valued than data creation. This needs however a cultural change very difficult to achieve that needs to confront the preference for creating new datasets, partially stemming from the fact that existing ones are not properly annotated, which hampers reuse. A more serious problem is that data producers may not even want to share data at all, which causes duplicate efforts when collecting data to do research on similar problems.

The bottom line is that metadata must include information about preservation/retention policies, and that it should be the responsibility of repositories to annotate records accordingly as data holders. Repositories should therefore be encouraged to put retention and preservation policies and procedures in place, and funders should instigate this by giving repository owners incentives to move in this direction, for example by linking funding streams to implementing policies or achieving quality according to criteria endorsed by communities.

²³ The OECD published a report on business models for data repositories, that could be relevant for this discussion: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/business-models-for-sustainable-research-data-repositories_302b12bb-en.html

Figure 10: Impressions from the round tables, Thematic Track 2.

7.2.2.2 Round Table 2: Data quality and supporting standards for the EOSC Federation (Chris Schubert, Matthias Löbe)

The discussion focused on whether knowledge graphs, such as those presented by Chris Schubert in Session A, can help create a “Data Quality label” for datasets. It is not clear whether a web-based quality assessment with ratings using e.g. “stars” would work in general.

Data quality is closely related to provenance, since users tend to regard data as having good quality if they come from a trusted source. Knowledge of where some dataset comes from, and how it was created, can help identify early on any problem it may have and reveal how it may be fixed. Provenance is also key to know whether data has been processed by AI, and discern the amount of human intervention on it. In addition, keeping track of intentional changes on datasets must be made visible too, as it can be used to prove authenticity, a key thing in e.g. cultural heritage²⁴. Metadata should be kept at any rate, since they enable characterising data in detail (like, for example, to indicate parts of datasets that are not to be trusted for whatever reason); also, technical metadata also serves to prevent vendor lock-in since it clarifies to all users how data is to be used regardless of any previous knowledge.²⁵

The importance of provenance depends however on the discipline, and it is difficult to dictate practices that should be followed in all areas. Indicating “fitness for use/purpose” of datasets may be a better solution than speaking in terms of data quality²⁶. Moreover, at present there is

²⁴ The project EOSC RAISE (<https://raise-science.eu/the-project/>) solves this by using blockchain technology: a hash that allows to prove data provenance without touching the data or metadata.

²⁵ Collection and publication of metadata do not however guarantee permission to use the data, as it is the case of health data (metadata are collected, but permission for reuse is not automatic).

²⁶ See the description of the Re-use Fitness model by EOSC EDEN in Andreassen H. et al. (2025). *D3.1 - Report on Discipline Requirements and Needs*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15789261>.

no standard vocabulary for data quality, and its value for end users is not clear. The usefulness of vocabularies is also questionable since data described with a vocabulary might attract companies, even if access cannot be granted to them. Normalisation (i.e., establishing some rules and following them) could help.

Regarding FAIR assessment, the goal should be to provide guidance rather than judgement to encourage improvement, since judgment risks disengaging researchers instead of helping them improve. The FAIR Assessment Interoperability Framework under development by OSTrails is conceived to work in this direction.

To enable progress a set of minimum requirements should be defined for descriptive, technical metadata, and provenance metadata. Communities and repositories seem interested in FAIR assessment, and repository managers would find useful to have a “global” FAIR assessment that indicates the quality of what a repository holds. Metadata are in fact an indication of data quality, in the sense that the richer they are, the more one can know about a dataset, which raises trust and therefore becomes an expression of quality, instead of requiring the validation of data itself, which is a difficult thing to do.

Zenodo, a widely used repository, has internal checks and balances such as MD5 checksums, which provide copy-level guarantees (but no long-term preservation checksums). Preservation is supported at bit level through ISO, although this alone is not sufficient to prevent or detect manipulation of the content.

In the case of health data, there is at present no requirements on researchers to ensure data quality to enable secondary use. The QUANTUM project is addressing this by enabling data producers to self-assess data quality. Star ratings awarded to datasets are not sure to be valid quality indicators (similar to recommender systems), since stars can be awarded even if all that is indicated is that there is no further info on the data.

One of the participants represented a repository hosting research data from seven publicly funded Latvian institutions. This repository has processes in place to ensure that the data hosted there comply with (not mandatory) quality requirements. The repository advises researchers on publishing datasets (where data should be published). They are working to get CTS involved in EOSC FIDELIS, to help ensure quality, even if it doesn’t involve getting an “official” endorsement. The repository is led by four largest universities, who have Data Stewards in place to help ensure that the data produced by researchers is fit for the repository. EGI aggregates information from repositories, but no data quality checks are performed.

7.2.2.3 Tools and policies for automated workflows to populate resources in the EOSC Federation with FAIR data (Daniel Garijo, Marek Cebecauer)

Round table 3 discussed tools and policies for automated workflows to populate resources in the EOSC Federation, based on the following list of questions:

- Which does it address?
- What is your service doing?
- How does it work? How can you achieve interoperability?
- Is there a curation process associated with automation?
- Standards and protocol?

- Granularity of the service/tool
- Link to EOSC/Metadata

On question 2, the group produced the following outcomes: The Finish data services are currently collecting the data in preservation, constructing new machinery, extending the catalogue, and collecting Life Science data, and trying to collect and reuse the data. Data Commons are aggregating data and tools and once there are combined, want to make it available for everyone. Data repositories are working to curate data in general.

With respect to interoperability, Marek Cebecauer stressed that in the current situation, ELNs (Electronic Lab Notebooks) tend to produce incompatible outputs, the most common format being PDF. To be sure, some ELNs produce reasonably structured JSON files, and very, very few which can link data. However, with the exception of the Swiss Standardization Institute, no one is really using publicly available JSON schemas to show what kind of data structure is implemented. On the other hand, the Swiss started before a decision on standards had been made, so it is not compatible. In Marek's presentation, he presented the idea that the output from an ELN should be an RO-Crate file containing DCAT-based cataloguing information, where the link would be a JSON LD.

7.2.3 Session C – Synthesising

The conclusions from Thematic Track 2 can be summarised as follows:

- Participants agree that research resources must carry sufficient metadata to qualify as Digital Objects that can be shared and found.
- ELNs are designed to be used by humans and are not necessarily machine-readable. Moreover, objects produced by ELNs are difficult to classify and lack vocabulary or W3C specification, which prevents their wide reuse.
- Knowledge Graphs can help display data quality, but implementation is not clear.
- What metadata should be required from data producers by repository operators to facilitate some form of data preservation is not clear, as is how this can be enabled, and who should be responsible. A suggestion is that information about retention policies and data quality commitments (including curation) should be shown by repositories for their preservation, rather than trying to embed it in Digital Objects.
- Health data are a particular type of personal data, with strict legal requirements from the EHDS regulation for secondary use that do not exist in other areas.
- Digital Objects from astrophysics can also be special (e.g. those from certain instruments that generate extremely large datasets, stored in distributed locations, and not directly reusable by researchers). For this community, it makes sense to establish workflows that people can just use to get datasets, even if they do not know all details about how it is actually done (researchers can be expected to have at least a limited understanding of what is going on underneath, but most users do not need it). The bottom line is that such workflows and protocols exist and are followed by practitioners.

7.3 Thematic Track 3: Competencies and Training

7.3.1 Introduction

To be able to fully adopt and benefit from the European Open Science Cloud, it is essential that researchers, research support professionals, and service providers across Europe have the appropriate competencies and skills. Furthermore, there is a need for coordination mechanisms and sustainable training infrastructure. And finally, by strengthening skills and engagement across all stakeholder groups, this will also support EOSC's broader objective of making Open Science the new normal.

The aim of the Competencies and Training Track was to bring together all stakeholders in the EOSC skills & training ecosystem to assess where we are and together define next steps to come to a EOSC skills and training roadmap. The session brought together around 40 participants from across the EOSC ecosystem, including EOSC Nodes, competence centres, research infrastructures, projects, training providers and EOSC policy developers.

Thematic Track 3 was composed of 3 sessions:

- Session A discussed the role and the contribution of the EOSC Academy to the EOSC Federation, to co-shape its design and delivery (in collaboration with EOSC Gravity), and share lessons learned from EOSC Nodes.
- Session B revolved around Embedding Training and Engagement in the EOSC Federation, to clarify synergies between competence centres, other training providers, and EOSC Nodes, as well as exploring options to improve training material discovery and catalogues.
- Session C aimed at developing an EOSC skills and training roadmap, by consolidating previous recommendations and those from Sessions A and B, as well as identifying and prioritising next steps for different stakeholder groups, and to create a draft mandate for a new Working Group on Competences and Training.

Discussions and identification of next steps focussed on 4 key themes:

- The role of the EOSC academy
- The role of Competence Centres in the EOSC ecosystem
- Training material discovery and catalogues
- A draft mandate for a new Working Group of the EOSC Federation

7.3.2 Session A – The role of the EOSC Academy and key priorities

Session A on the role of the EOSC Academy, was organised by Isabel Caetano, Eleni Toli, and Natalia Galica, and chaired by Kamran Naim. The session facilitator was Zoltán Pompor.

The session opened with a brief presentation by Eleni Toli from the EOSC-Gravity project on the aims and planned activities of the EOSC Academy, continued with presentations delivered by Roksana Wilk and Magdalena Szuflińska-Zurawska, Sara Pittonet-Gaiarin and Maja Dolinar presenting respectively the national Node of Poland, the thematic Node “Digital Twin of the Ocean” and the EU Node, and concluded with a panel discussion and of all presenters, with the participation of the audience, that was chaired by Kamran Naim.

The session focused on defining the role and contribution of the EOSC Academy within the broader EOSC Federation. Its primary goals were to present, discuss and co-shape the Academy's design and delivery. The Academy is designed as a collaborative initiative and a space for mutual learning and knowledge sharing, aimed at building a shared understanding of the EOSC Federation as a system of people and technical infrastructures. It intends to assist candidate Nodes and resource providers in participating in the Federation and to accelerate its overall development. In this process, the knowledge and previous experience by existing Nodes have been highlighted as very important.

Discussion revealed several operational challenges, such as limited IT capacity, fragmented training resources, and the lack of shared operational templates. To address these, participants identified critical skills and competences necessary for establishing a Node:

- **Legal aspects and legal support** were highlighted as primary needs.
- **Federated operations** and a deep understanding of the EOSC Federation structure.
- **IT skills and service management**, including the lifecycle management of products and services.
- **People skills**, including communication, networking, and team-playing abilities.
- **User engagement** and the ability to assess and understand user needs.

Participants discussed the content and types of activities they would like to see as part of the EOSC Academy offer. The list below summarises the main recommendations. In almost all answers and contributions, however, the emphasis was on practical and reusable materials:

- **Documentation:** Best practices, success stories, case studies, and "what didn't work" scenarios.
- **Operational Tools:** Legal templates, licensing models, service level agreements, and workflows for becoming a service provider.

Figure 11: Word cloud representing identified operational challenges.

- **Educational Resources:** Entry-level information (glossaries, "who is who"), professional materials explaining EOSC for reuse, and roadmap documentation for onboarding existing services.

- **Strategic Support:** Innovation management and alignment with EOSC policies.

When asked to prioritise training methods that should be implemented by the Academy, the peer-to-peer learning and the mentoring have been ranked very high. During the discussion it was clarified, however, that the training methods above need to be considered not as competitive and excluding one another, but complementary.

Finally, participants discussed what is needed to effectively train new EOSC Nodes on enrolment and onboarding. This got the unanimous reply that it is first necessary to understand the different stakeholders in the EOSC Federation ecosystem, including Nodes and service providers, as well as their roles and levels of maturity. A structured needs assessment (such as a targeted survey) should be conducted to identify knowledge gaps and priority areas.

Figure 12: Training methods to be prioritized by the EOSC Academy.

Moreover, training materials should be organised according to stages of engagement and stakeholder roles. This includes entry-level information (e.g. getting started guidance, key actors, glossary), more advanced support for existing or candidate Nodes (technical, legal, and policy aspects), and dedicated onboarding resources for candidate service providers.

In addition, a clear roadmap is needed to explain how a service can be onboarded into an existing Node, combining general Federation-level guidance with Node-specific requirements.

7.3.3 Session B – Embedding training and engagement in the EOSC Federation

Session B was organised and chaired by Emma Lazzeri and Friederike Schmidt-Tremmel. The session facilitator was Zoltán Pompor.

Session B aimed to explore how training, engagement, and competence-building can be embedded in the EOSC Federation by connecting Nodes, Competence Centres and other training providers with end-users to ensure that Open Science training enhances the uptake of the resources offered by the EOSC Nodes. In particular, it examined the role of competence centres (CCs), drawing on examples from thematic and national initiatives, and explored issues around training resource discovery.

The session started with brief lightning talks by selected Node representatives, including Oliver Knodel (PaNOSC, mTeSS-X), Gilles Mathieu (French CC) and Emma Lazzeri (Italian Node). The lightning talks were followed by a World Café Session, where tables discussed two topics: the role of Competence Centres in the EOSC Federation and Training Catalogues and Resource Discovery. Discussions and conclusions from each topic are outlined below.

7.3.3.1 The role of Competence Centres

Discussion on this topic focussed on the following questions:

- What are the roles in CCs? Which are essential, which ones are “nice to have”?
- What should be the main role of CCs in the Federation and what is their relation to the EOSC Nodes?
- What are the main barriers for the uptake of CCs in EOSC? What actions and collaborations are needed to overcome them and deliver real benefits in skills and training?

A key message is that while the EOSC Academy primarily serves Nodes, **CCs are closer to end users**, acting as trusted hubs that translate EOSC concepts into domain- and community-specific practice. Their aim is to provide material and training, give feedback to services, technical infrastructures, to act as bridges to researchers and institutional data stewards, and they often expand into broader research support, not limited to data management. Competence centres help identify user needs and route questions to the right expertise. Domain-specific CCs are essential to support specialised research communities.

CCs may have different roles, for example, event organisation and training delivery, training material curation and quality assurance and providing specialist expertise (such as data stewards / curators). CCs may work at different levels, for example, some working at institutional level (supporting research support staff, data curators) and others at national level and domain level (creating content and methodology for reuse).

Every EOSC Node should include a Competence Centre *function*, alongside IT infrastructure and services, offering skills for Open Science, for using the Nodes’ tools and services. It was felt that CCs are actually a federating capability. Participants stressed that competence centres are not helpdesks, but strategic enablers of skills development, including in emerging areas such as AI. However, it is important that CCs not formally linked to Nodes are still connected to the Federation.

Figure 13: The Thematic Track 3 subcommittee.

Final thoughts included that it is important to **focus on sustainability from the start**, embedding competence centre functions into Nodes. It is also important to understand the reasons to build competences, for CCs to think about what they offer and why. The national and local contexts that CCs provide are important to ensure relevance and adoption of EOSC services and resources. This should be underpinned by common methodologies and quality assurance for training resources, which should be outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook.

7.3.3.2 The Role of Training Catalogues

This topic focussed on the following questions:

- Which training and skills-based services/resources are most needed, and how can the Federation better support their development and delivery?
- Is training currently findable? Is an agreement on a single training platform needed? What would be the best way to catalogue existing material to ensure it is accessible? Do people need to point to relevant training? Is that one role for the CCs?
- What are the main barriers to the uptake of skills related services in EOSC? What concrete actions and collaborations are needed to overcome these barriers and deliver real benefits in skills and training?

Participants agreed that **one single catalogue is neither realistic nor desirable**. Instead, EOSC should support multiple training catalogues, with a flexible system depending on target communities, but connected through common approaches and standards.

There is a need to **differentiate between resources of a Node and training catalogues**. The training catalogue needs to have different metadata to allow resources to be findable. It could then be listed in the service catalogue of the Node as a service.

The content of the training catalogue needs to match the **needs of different audiences**, such as researchers, policy makers and leaders of research organisations. There could be different versions of the same content (social media posts, infographics, short read, deeper content). Catalogues could also support learning pathways tailored to communities or tasks, and incorporate user rating systems.

Figure 14: Impressions from Thematic Track 3.

Training materials should be treated like research data, following FAIR-by-Design principles, to enable reuse and discoverability. There needs to be agreement of a minimum set of metadata and global methodologies which should include common versioning, curation and quality assurance practices, supported by Train-the-Trainer programmes.

The next steps proposed include to develop and test a model for training catalogues in consultation with Nodes and relevant advisory groups, and integrate guidance competencies and skills requirements of nodes into the EOSC Federation Handbook.

7.3.4 Session C – Towards an EOSC skills and training roadmap

Session C was organised and chaired by Celia van Gelder, Helen Clare and Isabel Caetano. The session facilitator was Zoltán Pompor.

Celia opened the session by summarising the progress and developments in skills and training. Much work has been done in the past by many stakeholders, a.o. by the EOSC Working Group Skills & Training that produced the report "Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science" (2021²⁷), the EOSC Task Forces in the period 2021-2023. OAEG5, active since 2024, has identified thematic

²⁷ EC DG RTD and EOSC Executive Board, Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science, *Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*, Barker, M. et al. (eds.), Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>.

work streams and produced recommendations for next steps at the 2024 and 2025 EOSC Winter Schools²⁸.

This means that there is a lot of groundwork done to build on when working towards an EOSC skills and training roadmap, which aims to ensure that all actors in the EOSC skills and training ecosystem take up their roles in developing, delivering, and sustaining skills and training needed for FAIR, Open, and reproducible research across Europe. With the EOSC Federation now entering the implementation phase it becomes crucial to work towards a joint strategy, because without proper skills for & engagement from all stakeholders the benefits of EOSC can not be realized.

The next topic was the information related to training formulated in the EOSC Federation Handbook. The Handbook recognizes that training material for research services and other services is essential for scientists to use them properly, and should be made available as an integral part of service delivery and discoverable via thematic/domain/national/institutional training platforms. However, it was noted that the information about training and training services in the Handbook is currently very limited, and that more guidance is needed for EOSC Nodes to shape their training offer in the Federation.

After this the group consolidated the outcomes and next steps for the themes EOSC Academy, CCs and Training Catalogues previously discussed in separate World Cafe tables. The outcomes have already been included in the summaries of Session A and B above.

In the final part of Session C, the main goal was to formulate collaboratively a draft for the mandate for the new working group for Competencies and Training under the new structure as defined in the MoU. The mandate needs to indicate how the working group will contribute to the Federation in 2026 as it transitions to production, and define tangible deliverables.

In addition, for a WG to start, a minimum of 5 Nodes that endorse the mandate is needed. To identify the interest of the (emerging) EOSC Nodes in the establishment of this WG, 16 Nodes were contacted in the period before the Winter School to collect their interest. Almost all Nodes expressed interest to support and actively contribute to the formulation of the Working Group and its mandate, however no formal commitment was requested from them now. The objective of the WG was formulated as follows:

- Improving integration of skills and training in the Federation, including both Nodes and end user training
- Define and promote the ecosystem of training for the EOSC Federation
- Provide contributions to the EOSC Academy, CCs and the Users Forum

In terms of expected output, participants suggested the following:

- Deliverables 2026:
 - Minimal metadata schema for training (events/materials/methodology)
 - Pilot for metadata transfer from sources like catalogue/registry/website into the EOSC EU node catalogue

²⁸ Rey Mazón, M., & Hasani-Mavriqi, I. (2024). *Report on the EOSC Winter School 2024*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15055465>; Reichmann, S., Rey Mazón, M., & Hasani-Mavriqi, I. (2025). *Report on the EOSC Winter School 2025*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15101262>

- Defined competencies and skills requirements for nodes and services in the EOSC Federation Handbook
- A model of the structure and integration of competences and skills in EOSC Nodes and Federation

The Working Group should be composed of training specialists from the Nodes and liaisons and guests from OA5EG and relevant EOSC projects . These outcomes will be taken forward to the Node Coordinators Committee after the Winter School.

7.3.5 Conclusions

Track 3 concluded that competencies and training are fundamental to making EOSC truly functional and sustainable. Participants agreed that clearer roles, stronger coordination, and shared methodologies are needed across the EOSC Academy, Competence Centres, and training catalogues. The discussions highlighted the importance of improving findability and quality of training resources, strengthening user engagement, and ensuring that skills development becomes an integrated part of every EOSC Node. Overall, the track set the foundation for a more coherent, user-centred, and long-term EOSC skills and training ecosystem, supported by a new dedicated Working Group.

8 Annex II: Programme Committee and Programme Subcommittees

8.1 Programme Committee

The Programme Committee for the EOSC Winter School 2026 was formed in September 2025, to guide the development of the Winter School Programme, through defining strategic goals, high-level topics, and approaches, and by convening the Programme Subcommittees. The Programme Committee consisted of representatives from EOSC-A, the EOSC Federation Build-up Group, and the EOSC Gravity project, respectively, as follows:

Name	Organisation	Projects	Other
Klaus Tochtermann	ZBW/EOSC-A		
Ute Gunsenheimer	EOSC Association	EOSC Gravity, EOSC United	
Bob Jones	EOSC Association	EOSC United	EOSC Federation Build-up Group
Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi	TU Graz	EOSC Gravity	
Stefan Reichmann	TU Graz	EOSC Gravity	
Ilaria Nardello	EOSC-A		
Monika Góral-Kurbiel	NCN	EOSC Gravity	

Table 1: Programme Committee members

8.2 Organising Committee

Name	Organisation	Projects	Other
Ute Gunsenheimer	EOSC Association	EOSC Gravity, EOSC United	
Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi	TU Graz	EOSC Gravity	
Stefan Reichmann	TU Graz	EOSC Gravity	
Miguel Rey Mazón	TU Graz	EOSC Gravity	
Mélanie Collot	Kellen Company/EOSC-A		
Ivett Letenovics	EOSC-A		
Sara Pittonet Gaiarin	Trust-IT	EOSC Gravity	
Lenka Unge	EOSC-A		
Monika Góral-Kurbiel	NCN	EOSC Gravity	

Table 2: Organizing Committee members

8.3 Programme Subcommittees

8.3.1 Thematic Track 1: Federating Capabilities and Interoperability

Thematic Track 1 featured subcommittee members from OAEGs 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively, as follows:

Name	OAEGs	EOSC-A TFs	Projects
Esteban Gonzalez	OAEG2	TF1	FAIR2ADAPT, OSTRAILS, EVERSE
Diego Scardaci	OAEG4	TF1	EOSC Beyond, EOSC DataCommons, EOSC United, EOSC Gravity
Simon Hodson	OAEG2		CA4EOSC, CDIF4XAS
Wolmar N Åkerström	OAEG2/3	TF3 Health Data	EOSC-ENTRUST
Clement Jonquet	OAEG2		FAIR-IMPACT, FIDELIS
Matthias Löbe	OAEG2	Health Data, FAIR Metrics & Digital objects	
Marek Cebecauer	OAEG1/3	TF2	
Tibor Kalman	OAEG1/3		
Alexandra Kokkinaki	OAG2	TF1	Blue-Cloud, RAISE Suite
Tomasz Miksa		TF1	OSTrails
Roksana Wilk	OAEG2	TF1	EOSC Beyond, EOSC Data Commons

Table 3: Programme Subcommittee Thematic Track 1

8.3.2 Thematic Track 2: Resources

Thematic Track 2 featured subcommittee members from OAEGs 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively, as follows:

Name	OAEGs	EOSC-A TFs	Projects
Raul Palma	OA2	FAIR Metrics and Digital objects	Fair2Adapt, OStrails
Sebastian Luna-Valero	OA4		EOSC Data Commons
Fen Zhang		Long-term data retention	EOSC EDEN
Jacques Flores		Long-term data retention	
Fotis Psomopoulos	OA7		EVERSE
Wolmar N Åkerström	OA2	Health Data	
Chris Schubert	OA3	FAIR Metrics and Digital objects	
Marek Cebecauer	OAEG1/3	FAIR Metrics and Digital objects	
Matthias Löbe	OA2	FAIR Metrics & Digital objects, Health Data	
Giacinto Donvito			
Fernando Aguilar		FAIR Metrics and Digital objects	SIESTA, FIDELIS
Nicola Fiore	OA4		EOSC BEYOND
Baptiste Cecconi	OA4	EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability	EXTRACT
Daniel Garijo	OA3		

Table 4: Programme Subcommittee Thematic Track 2

8.3.3 Thematic Track 3: Competencies and Training

Thematic Track 2 featured subcommittee members from OAEs 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively, as follows:

Name	OAEs	EOOSC-A TFs	Projects
Isabel Caetano	OA5		EOOSC Gravity (Academy)
Helen Clare	OAE5		None
Celia van Gelder	OAE5		EOOSC4Cancer, EOOSC-Life
Natalia Galica	OAE5		EOOSC Gravity
Austine Phiri	OAE5		
Krzysztof Poterlowicz	OAE5/7		
Hanna Lindroos	OAE5		
Kamran Naim			
Friederike Schmidt-Tremmel	OAE5		OSCARS
Sara Di Giorgio	OAE5		Skills4EOOSC
Emma Lazzeri	OAE5		Skills4EOOSC
Eleni Toli			EOOSC Gravity

Table 5: Programme Subcommittee Thematic Track 3

9 Annex III: Winter School Participants and Representation across projects, OAEs, and EOSC-A Task Forces

9.1 List of participating projects

Project	Project/Technical Coordinator	Organisation	Website
AquaINFRA	Arne Berre	Aalborg University	https://aquainfra.eu/
Beyond	Hien Bui (coord.), Diego Scardaci (techn. coord.)	EGI	https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/
Blue-Cloud 2026	Sara Pittonet (coord.), Dick Schaap (techn. coord.)	CNR	https://www.blue-cloud.org/
ClimateAdapt	Thanasis Sfetsos	National Centre for Scientific Research "DEMOKRITOS"	https://climate-adapt4eosc.eu/
Data Commons	Diego Scardaci	EGI	https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu/
DataGEMS	Georgia Koutrika	Athena RC	https://datagems.eu/
EDEN	Damien LeCarpentier, Sara Garavelli	CSC	https://eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-eden/
ENTRUST	Peter MacCallum (coord./techn. coord.)	ELIXIR Hub	https://eosc-entrust.eu/
EVERSE	F. Psomopoulos (coord./techn. coord.), S. Capella-Gutierrez, T. Vergoulis, N. Manola	CERTH	https://everse.software/
FAIR2Adapt	Anne Fouilloux	Simula Research Laboratory	https://fair2adapt-eosc.eu/
FIDELIS	Damien LeCarpentier, Sara Garavelli	CSC	https://eosc.eu/eu-project/fidelis/
GRAVITY	Ute Gunsenheimer (coord.)	EOSC Association	https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/
Lumen	Suzanne Dumouchel (coord.)	CNRS	https://lumenproject.eu/
OSCARS	Giovanni Lamanna (coord.)	CNRS-LAPP	https://oscars-project.eu/
OSTrails	Natalia Manola (coord.), Tomasz Miksa (techn. coord.)	OpenAIRE	https://ostrails.eu/
RAISE	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (techn. coord.)	Aristotle University Thessaloniki	https://raise-science.eu/
RAISE Suite	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (techn. coord.)	Aristotle University Thessaloniki	https://raise-science.eu/
SIESTA	Alvaro Lopez Garcia (techn. coord.)	CSIC	https://eosc-siesta.eu/

Project	Project/Technical Coordinator	Organisation	Website
STR-ESFRI	Fotis Karayannis (coord.), Panagiota Koltsida (techn coord.)	Athena RC	https://www.esfri.eu/objectives-mission
TITAN	Antonio Skarmeta (coord./techn. coord.)	Universidad deMurcia	https://titan-eosc.eu/
United	Bob Jones (coord.)	EOSC Association	https://eosc.eu/eosc-united

Table 6: EOSC-related projects represented at the EOSC Winter School 2026.

9.2 Thematic Track Participants

9.2.1 Thematic Track 1 - Federating Capabilities and Interoperability

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Ilire	Hasani-Mavriqi	Graz University of Technology	GRAVITY	None	none
Rudolf	Dimper	Rudolf Dimper	None	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Tomasz	Miksa	TU Wien & SBA Research	OSTrails	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Baptiste	Cecconi	Observatoire de Paris	OSTrails	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Pierre	le Sidaner	Observatoire de Paris	OSTrails	OAEG4	none
Andreas	Rauber	ASC-RC (TUWIEN)	OSCARS	OAEG3	none
Maja	Dolinar	OpenAIRE AMKE	United	None	LT Data Retention
Lauren	Maxwell	Universitätsklinikum Heidelberg	None	OAEG2	Health Data
Katharina	Flicker	ASC (TU Wien)	None	None	none
Thanasis	Sfetsos	NCSR Demokritos	ClimateAdapt	OAEG3	none
Lukasz	Opiola	ACC Cyfronet AGH	Data Commons	None	none
Natalia	Manola	OpenAIRE	OSTrails	OAEG6	none
Patrick	Ruch	SIB & HES-SO	FIDELIS	OAEG6	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Suzanne	Dumouchel	EOSC-A	Lumen	OAEG6	none
Stefan	Reichmann	Graz Univ. of Technology	GRAVITY	None	none
Hervé	L'Hours	CESSDA, UK Data Service, Univ Essex	FIDELIS	OAEG3	LT Data Retention
Johanna	Laiho-Kauranne	CSC	OSTrails	OAEG4	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Esteban	González Guardia	UPM	FAIR2Adapt	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Mark	Dietrich	Bloodstone Consulting OÜ	Beyond	OAEG2	none
Dimitra	Panou	Natl Centre For Scientific Research Demokritos	ClimateAdapt	OAEG3	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Ingrid	Dillo	DANS	FIDELIS	None	none

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Thomas	Jouneau	INRAE / Recherche Data Gouv	FIDELIS	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Christelle	Pierkot	CNRS	Lumen	None	none
Julien	Homo	FoXCub	Lumen	None	none
Lukas	Vojacek	IT4Innovations, Tech. Univ. of Ostrava	ENTRUST	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Kacper	Donat	Gdańsk University of Technology	FIDELIS	None	none
Anders	Sjöström	Lund University	None	None	none
Nicola	Fiore	EGI FOUNDATION	Beyond	OAEG4	none
Nils	Hoffmann	FZJ	United	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Stéphane	Erard	Observatoire de Paris	OSCARS	None	none
Sanjay Kumar	Srikakulam	FZJ	United	None	none
Tobias	Herb	SINTEF	AquaINFRA	None	none
Franciska	de Jong	CLARIN ERIC	OSTrails	OAEG5	none
Vania	Virgili	E-RIHS ERIC	None	None	none
Flavius	Pana	REA	None	None	none
Barbara	Magagna	GO FAIR Foundation	FAIR2Adapt	OAEG2	none
Luděk	Matyska	CESNET	United	None	none
Balázs	Pataki	HUN-REN	None	None	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
László	Kovács	HUN-REN	None	OAEG2	none
Peter	Maccallum	ELIXIR	ENTRUST	None	none
Zdenka	Dudova	CESNET	None	None	none
Anastas	Mishev	Ss. Cyril & Methodius Univ Skopje	Beyond	None	none
Valerio	Piomponi	Area Science Park	None	None	none
David	Lloyd	ELIXIR Europe	United	None	none
Daniel	Garijo	UPM	OSTrails	OAEG3	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Guido	Aben	SUNET	None	None	none
Jérôme	Pansanel	IPHC / CNRS / Univ. of Strasbourg	SIESTA	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Sara	Pittonet Gaiarin	Trust-IT Services	Blue-Cloud2026	None	none
Peter	Lényi	Masaryk University	United	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Heinrich	Widmann	DKRZ	AquaINFRA	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Quesneville	Hadi	INRAE	None	None	none
Kaspars	Bērziņš	VPC	None	None	none
Kristyna	Kvizdova	Masaryk University	ENTRUST	None	none
Roksana	Wilk	Cyfronet	Beyond	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Elli	Papadopoulou	Athena RC	OSTrails	OAEG3	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Ahmed	Saleh	ZBW Leibniz	None	None	none
Mélanie	Collot	EOSC Association	None	None	none
Lassi	Lager	CSC	None	None	none

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Bob	Jones	EOSC-A	United	None	none
Jonathan	Tedds	ELIXIR Hub	ENTRUST	OAEG7	Long-Term Data Retention
Panagiota	Koltsida	Athena RC	STR-ESFRI	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Wolmar	Nyberg Åkerström	NBIS	ENTRUST	OAEG2	Health Data
Bo	Bai	DeiC	None	None	none
Cymon	Cox	Centro de Ciencias do Mar (CCMAR)	None	None	none
Enol	Fernández	EGI Foundation	DataCommons	None	none
Ondrej	Prancl	CESNET	None	None	none
Diego	Scardaci	EGI Foundation	Beyond	OAEG4	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Lise	Schröder	Aalborg University	AquaINFRA	None	none
Elena	Sokolova	OPERAS	Lumen	None	none
Ana Teresa	Mota	EC - DG RTD	None	None	none
Chris	Schubert	TU Wien	Beyond	OAEG3	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Themis	Zamani	GRNET	Beyond	OAEG1	none
Jiří	Marek	Masaryk University	United	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Tibor	Kálmán	GWDG	Beyond	OAEG1	none
Marc	Portier	VLIZ vzw	Blue-Cloud 2026	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Federica	Bazzocchi	Area Science Park	None	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Petr	Holub	BBMRI-ERIC	None	OAEG2	Health Data
Mattias	Levlin	CSC	EDEN	None	none
Mark	van de Sanden	GÉANT	None	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Alexandra	Kokkinaki	Natl Oceanography Centre, BODC	RAISE Suite	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Patricia	Mergen	Meise Botanic Garden	None	None	none
Björn	Grüning	Universität Freiburg	DataCommons	OAEG4	none
Veronika	Ambrozova	Masaryk University	Beyond	None	Health Data
Antje	Keppler	Euro-Biolmaging	OSCARS	None	none
Carlo	Lacagnina	EOSC-A	United	None	none
Marcus	Povey	Instruct-ERIC	United	None	none
Josefine	Nordling	CSC	None	OAEG1	none
Milan	Ojstersek	University of Maribor	None	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Karl	Presser	Premotec GmbH	Beyond	OAEG3	LT Data Retention
Vincent	Emonet	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	DataCommons	None	none
Andreas	Türk	BBMRI-ERIC	None	None	none
Georgia	Koutrika	Athena RC	DataGEMS	None	none

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Klaus	Tochtermann	EOSC Association	None	None	none
Tommi	Suominen	CSC	None	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Anaïs	Guillem	E-RIHS ERIC	None	None	none
Ahmad	Zein Assi	UniDistance Suisse	None	None	none
Henning Sten	Hansen	Aalborg University	AquaINFRA	OAEG2	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Federica	Tanlongo	EPOS ERIC	None	OAEG5	none
Urpo	Kaila	CSC	None	None	none
Mark	Allen	Obs. astronomique de Strasbourg	OSCARS	None	none
Ilja	Afanasjevs	VPC	None	None	none
Tomáš	Heryán	Technical Univ Ostrava, CEET Ctr.	None	OEG7	none
Yann	Le Franc	e-Science Data Factory	Lumen	None	none
Rafał	Bartczuk	Children's Memorial Health Institute	None	None	Health Data
Ivett	Letenovics	EOSC Association	None	None	none
Jessica	Parland-von Essen	CSC	None	None	none
Natalia	Borgoños Garcia	University of Murcia	TITAN	None	none
María	Hernández Padilla	University of Murcia	TITAN	None	none
Lenča	Ambrožič	Arnes	None	None	none
Paolo	Manghi	OpenNAIRE	OSTrails	OAEG2	Tech& Sem Interoperability
Tjerk	Krijger	MARIS B.V.	Blue-Cloud 2026	OAEG2	none
Simon	Hodson	CODATA	ClimateAdapt	OAEG2	none
Patrycja	Antosz	NORCE Research AS	None	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Laurence	Desnos	EOSC-A	None	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Navtej	Juty	Univ. Manchester	ClimateAdapt	OAEG1	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Gorka	Epelde	Biogipuzkoa Health Research Institute	RAISE Suite	OAEG1	Health Data
Rebecca	Kröhler	NFDI	None	None	none
Wim	Hugo	Personal	DataCommons	OAEG1	none

Table 7: Thematic Track 1 - full list of participants.

9.2.2 Thematic Track 2 - Resources

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Marek	Cebecauer	Heyrovsky Institute	None	OAEG1	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Sylvia	Jeney	SNSF	None	OAEG3	none
Kaori	Otsu	CREAF	AquaINFRA	OAEG4	none

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Miroslav	Ruda	CESNET	Beyond	None	Health Data
Marion	MASSOL	INRAE	None	None	none
Giuseppe	Magnifico	CNR	None	None	none
Witold	Arndt	DLR	None	None	LT Data Retention
Nathalie	Fargier	CNRS - HAL & Episciences	Data Commons	OAEG6	none
Miguel	Rey Mazón	Graz Univ. of Technology	GRAVITY	None	none
Wilko	Steinhoff	DANS	EDEN	None	none
Matthew	Viljoen	EGI Foundation	Beyond	None	none
Juan	González-García	IACS	United	None	Health Data
Kristaps	Oškalns	VPC	None	None	none
Claudia	D'Onofrio	Trust-It Services	GRAVITY	OAEG4	none
Juha	Lehtonen	CSC	EDEN	None	none
Jacques	Flores	Utrecht University	None	None	LT Data Retention
Ulf	Jakobsson	Univ of Gothenburg / SND	None	None	LT Data Retention
Fabio	Liberante	EMBL-EBI/ELIXIR	FIDELIS	None	none
Kostas	Koumantaros	GRNET S.A.	Beyond	None	none
Evdokimos	Konstantinidis	Aristotle Univ. of Thessaloniki	RAISE	OAEG1	none
Jean-Yves	Le Meur	CERN	EDEN	OAEG2	LT Data Retention
Sebastian	Luna-Valero	EGI Foundation	DataCommons	OAEG4	none
Anja	Busch	ZBW	None	None	none
Fernando	Aguilar Gómez	IFCA-CSIC	SIESTA	OAEG3	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Roxanne	Wyns	KU Leuven	EDEN	OAEG3	none
Monika	Góral-Kurbiel	NCN	GRAVITY	None	none
Jorge	Bernal-Romero	IACS	United	None	none
ilaria	Nardello	EOSC Association	GRAVITY	None	none
Matthias	Löbe	Univ. Leipzig	None	OAEG2	Health Data
Ivan	Lambov	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	None	None	none
Sarmite	Mickevica	Ministry of Education and Science	None	None	none

Table 8: Thematic Track 2 - Full list of participants.

9.2.3 Thematic Track 3 - Competencies and Training

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Hanna	Lindroos	Swedish Univ of Agricultural Sciences	None	OAEG5	none
Barbara	Sanchez	TU Wien	OSTrails	OAEG5	none
Elena	Giglia	Univ. of Turin	None	OAEG6	none
Isabel	Caetano	EOSC-A	GRAVITY	OAEG5	none

Name	Last Name	Organisation	Project(s)	OAEG	EOSC-A TF
Victoria	Dominguez Del Angel	Inria	OSTrails	OAEG5	none
Friederike	Schmidt-Tremmel	Trust-IT Srl	OSCARS	OAEG5	none
Magdalena	Szuflita-Zurawska	Gdańsk Univ. of Technology	FIDELIS	OAEG5	none
Emma	Lazzeri	CNR	None	OAEG5	none
Vladimira	Coufalova	J. Heyrovsky Inst. of Physical Chem.	STR-ESFRI	None	none
Veronique	Stoll	Ministry of Research	FIDELIS	OAEG1	none
Mariarita	de Luca	Area Science Park	None	OAEG5	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Celia	van Gelder	Health-RI	None	OAEG5	none
Gilles	Mathieu	Ministry of HE and Research	FIDELIS	None	none
Romain	David	ERINHA	OSCARS	OAEG5	FAIR Metrics & Digital Objects
Xavier	Salazar Forn	EGI Foundation	DataCommons	None	none
Oliver	Knodel	HZDR	EVERSE	None	none
Eleni	Toli	ATHENA RC	GRAVITY	OAEG5	none
Jordi	Bodera Sempere	ESRF	OSCARS	OAEG5	none
Sigrid	Gåseidnes	Sikt	None	None	none
NATALIA	GALICA	NCN	GRAVITY	OAEG6	none
Helen	Clare	Jisc	None	OAEG5	none
Jessica	Lindvall	Science for Life Laboratory	None	OAEG5	none
Zoltán	Pompor	Pro-M Ltd.	None	None	none
Diana	Marek	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	FIDELIS	OAEG5	none
Eleni	Petra	ELENI PETRA	DataGEMS	OAEG7	none
Inês	Caramelo	Univ. of Coimbra	None	None	none
Norbert	Meyer	PCSS	None	None	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Thomas	Mackenzie	G.A.C. Group	ClimateAdapt	OAEG5	none
Marialuisa	Lavitrano	Univ. Milano Bicocca	None	OAEG5	Health Data
Ute	Gunsenheimer	EOSC Association	GRAVITY	None	none
Kollol	Chakraborty	Technovative Solutions Ltd.	ClimateAdapt	OAEG7	Tech & Sem Interoperability
Sushma	Grellscheid	University of Bergen	Beyond	OAEG3	none
Ulriika	Vihervalli	CSC	United	OAEG1	none
Dimitri	Prandner	Johannes Kepler Univ. Linz	None	OAEG5	none

Table 9: Thematic Track 3 - Full list of participants.

Report on the EOSC Winter School 2026

Find out more:

